

Bionomics and geographical distribution of the Hungarian Cochylini species (Lepidoptera, Tortricidae)

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Abstract. First part of a series of papers on the bionomics and geographical distribution of Hungarian Tortricidae species. This is the first atlas in Hungary summarising the records of 83 species. This study presents partial flight data, food plants and preferred habitats of Cochylini species. Detailed distribution maps are shown for each species.

Keywords. Biology, habitat, range, distribution maps, remarks

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Introduction

Scientific research on the Hungarian Lepidoptera fauna began in the second half of the 1700s with the work of Giovanni Antonio Scopoli (1723–1788). In 1769, Scopoli was appointed Professor of Chemistry and Metallurgy at the Mining Academy at Schemnitz (an old, historic Hungarian town, now Banská Štiavnica, Slovakia), and in 1777 transferred to the University of Pavia. Scopoli corresponded with Carl Linnaeus, the Swedish botanist and zoologist who laid the foundations of modern taxonomy. Linnaeus greatly respected him and showed great interest in his work, though because of the great distance, they never met.

Scopoli, during his stay in Hungary, described *Nycteola revayana* (Scopoli, 1872) [= *Tortrix revayana*]. Subsequently, several Hungarian collectors published their research results in small publications. For more information, see the publication in Hungarian and Latin by Abafi-Aigner et al. in 1896.

Abafi-Aigner et al. (1986), in their book "Fauna Regni Hungariae", reviewed for the first time the Lepidoptera fauna of historical Hungary. This is the first publication in which we have information on the Hungarian Lepidoptera fauna.

Historically, Hungary was three times larger (325 411 km²) than the present territory – the changes being made by the Treaty of Trianon (4 June 1920). From this vast geographical area, the authors have identified 2628 Lepidoptera species, including 304 of Tortricidae. The importance of the latter will be emphasised later. In the area of present-day Hungary (93 030 km²), 3,550 species have been documented by recent research (Pastoralis et al. 2016). After 2016, several new species have been recorded in the country (see references). This present text focuses on the Hungarian Tortricidae fauna.

The "Fauna Hungariae" series of books, which began publication in the 1950s, is well-known to lepidopterist researchers. Many volumes were published, but in the 1990s the series ceased publication. The cited reasons include financial and organisational difficulties, but the primary reason was a lack of interest. I note that the so-called "Microlepidoptera" volumes have been published continuously based on the excellent work of László Gozmány (1953–1965). However, László Gozmány did not undertake to write the volume Tortricidae. This volume is still very much missing in Hungarian fauna research. I have personally consulted László Gozmány several times about the writing of the Hungarian Tortricidae volume, but the discussions were fruitless. Therefore, in the early 1980s, I started to study the Hungarian Tortricidae fauna on my own (Fazekas 1981–2023). In the late 1990s, I approached the editor-in-chief of the Fauna Hungariae book series and offered to write the Hungarian Tortricidae volume. I was

informed that there was no money to publish the volume. I should write it, but they could not support it financially.

Thirty years have passed since then, and it became clear that the *Fauna Hungariae* book series will not continue. It was then that I decided to write a volume of the Hungarian Tortricidae fauna myself, based on 40 years of research, with a new concept and new methods. The present work is the first part of the final book. In smaller taxonomic groups, I present the bionomics of the Hungarian species and their geographical distributions in this country and give an overview of the Palearctic areas. Where necessary, species are annotated. For each species, I provide a map of its distribution in Hungary. For the map representation, I use the Hungarian natural geographic landscape classification (Marosi, Somogyi 1990, Dömény 2010). This map type shows the topography, hydrology, vegetation, and general ecology of Hungary better than a simple UTM Grid map, where only points indicate the occurrence of species.

I used this mapping methodology in my books "*Sesiidae fauna of Hungary*" (Fazekas 2017) and "*The Eupitheciini of Hungary*" (Fazekas 2020). This is a completely new mapping concept in Hungary. My Tortricidae studies, and the planned book, are nothing like the "*Fauna Hungariae*" series of books, the concepts of which were conceived in the 1950s but are no longer useful in the 21st century. One of these "old-fashioned", very slow practices was the drawing of species habitus images in black ink. This can be easily replaced by computer-based digital techniques (see Fazekas 2009, 2017, 2020).

Current research suggests that 480–490 species of Tortricidae are known in Hungary. The occurrence of several is only known from old literature and no authentic specimens have been found in Hungarian collections. Many specimens collected in Hungary are preserved mainly in Austrian, German, Italian, English and other collections so the Hungarian practice of including only those species present in one of the Hungarian collections is wrong. This problem should be further investigated.

This paper is the first part of the presentation of the Hungarian Tortricidae fauna and discusses the Tribe Cochylini.

Material and methods

I started my research in the early 1980s. In these 40 years I have collected moths in all-natural geographic regions of Hungary. I have studied habitats, feeding plants of species, and flight periods. The collections were mainly made with evening lights and light traps, mostly 160-watt HMLI and 125-watt mercury vapour lamps. I also collected specimens by daytime netting and beating of vegetation.

From 1896 to 2021 I critically processed the literature on Tortricidae species. I visited and examined the most important museums and private collections in Hungary. For accurate and authentic identification, I have made thousands of genital examinations.

Genitalia dissections were made according to Robinson (1976). Some of the genitalia were mounted in Euparal on slides; others were preserved in micro-vials filled with glycerol. Genital analysis of worn, damaged specimens of Cochylini was performed using the simple and rapid method of Fazekas (2020, 2021), and Wanke & Rajaei (2018).

I thought it important to present a more thorough description of the genus diagnosis, especially based on the work of Razowski (1970, 2009, 2011). This is also important because there are many anomalies in the Hungarian literature on this topic. In a historical overview of Hungarian literature, there is confusion not only in the naming of genera or species but also in the identification of taxa. One of the main reasons for this is that Hungarian researchers have done little or no genital studies.

The data of the Hungarian distribution maps are stored in a computer database, partly in Word and Excel formats.

The vector maps were created with CorelDraw. The digital maps are interactive and can be continuously updated and corrected.

The identification of the Cochylini specimens was done by myself. The identified specimens are deposited in the following collections:

Bakonyi Természettudományi Múzeum, Zirc | Bakony Natural History Museum, Zirc

Janus Pannonius Múzeum, Pécs | Janus Pannonius Museum, Pécs,
 Jász Múzeum, Jászberény | Jász Museum, Jászberény
 Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum, Budapest | Hungarian Natural History Museum
 [HNHM], Budapest
 Mátra Múzeum, Gyöngyös | Mátra Museum, Gyöngyös
 Pannon Intézet, Pécs | Pannon Institute, Pécs,
 Rippl-Rónai Múzeum, Kaposvár | Rippl-Rónai Museum, Kaposvár
 Természettudományi Gyűjtemény, Komló | Natural History Collection, Komló

A Brief Account of Hungarian Landscape Types

The hierarchical order of Hungarian natural landscapes was proposed 34 years ago (Marosi, Somogyi, 1990). Everybody has accepted the system that contains microregions, microregion groups, mesoregions and macroregions. While there are occasional minor disputes about the borderlands, these do not affect the core concept. I have recorded the geographical distribution of the taxa according to the six Hungarian macroregions (Fig 2.). The geographical distribution of the taxa is exceedingly different in certain regions.

Text-fig. 1. Detailed topographic map of Hungary without inscriptions. The main designations are shown in Figure 2. The circles on the map show the main Cochylini research regions. It can be seen that a large part of the lowland areas is poorly known. The mountain areas are the best known. The Cochylini fauna of the hilly landscapes is also only partially known. Only sporadic observations have been made in the areas close to the national border.

Text-fig. 2. Major natural landscapes in Hungary where Cochylini observations were made. Detailed descriptions are given in the text.

(1) The Great Hungarian Plain

Flat plains, 75–200 m. Plain with a moderately continental climate, landscape types are predominantly used for agriculture. On the Great Hungarian Plain one finds a more severe summer microclimate than that is generally prevalent in forested regions of central Europe since the combination of open steppe and soda flats produces often relatively high surface temperatures during the summer. Average temperatures for the plain are 22°C in July and -2°C in January. Recorded maximum and minimum extremes are about 39°C and -28°C. Natural vegetation: oak forests and grassland on the sand, loess steppe, alkaline vegetation on solonchak alluvial forests and swamps. The Hungarian plain is perhaps a typical example of the steppe or other grassland habitats favoured by many *Phteochroa*, as far as it is known, although the moths may prefer slight hillsides on the periphery of steppes.

(2) Little Plain

Flat plains, 75–200 m. Alluvial plain; cultivated grassland with a high groundwater table and hygromorphous soils. Natural vegetation: alluvial forests and swamps, and at higher elevations oak forests and grassland on the sand as well as loess steppe.

(3) West Hungarian Borderland

Valleys, foothills, medium-height mountains with broad ridges, 150–883 m. Eroded hills in the sub-alpine regions on brown loess and pseudogley soils with mosaics of forests mixed with Scot's pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) partly used for agriculture, as well as eroded hills (250–350) with estivated brown forest soil on brown loess; partly used for agriculture. Natural vegetation: mainly Illyrian oak-hornbeam forests, as well as Illyrian beech forests and oak forests, mixed with Scot's pine.

(4) Transdanubian Hills

Valleys, hills, foothills, medium-height mountains, 150–682 m. Mainly in the west, fixed sandy plain with minor dunes, cultivated grassland on brown earth, local afforestation, and orchards. In the east at first independent hilly regions were dissected by eroded valleys, mostly cultivated grassland with deep groundwater tables, vineyards, and major remnants of mixed forests. In the south, forested landscape types in mountains of medium height (Mecsek Mts, Villány Hills); calcareous rock or sandstone with rendzina and passivated brown forest soils, typically with *Tilio argenteae-Quercetum* or Illyrian oak-hornbeam forests (*Helleboro Carpinetum*), and mosaic Illyrian karst with downy oak, karst shrub-forest and rocky swards.

(5) Transdanubian Mountains

Medium-height mountains, 200–756 m. mainly low mountains under additional sub-Atlantic and sub-Mediterranean climatic influence. *Quercetum-petraeae-cerris* and *Qu. petraeae-Carpinetum* forests. In part hills were dissected by eroded valleys; cultivated grassland with a mosaic of vineyards and orchards *Quercetum-petraeae-cerris* forests and a deep groundwater table. On the mountain slopes are many kinds of karst shrub forests and rock swards, e.g., in the Bakony Mts, the Vértes Mts. and the Budai Mts.

(6) North Hungarian Mountains

Medium-height mountains, 300–1015 m. Extremely variable landscape type. In one respect a characteristic is the crests of volcanic mountains with black "nyirok" (regolith) and podsollic brown forest soil, submontane beech forests (silviculture with touristic and recreational use Mátra Mts, Zemplén Mts). On the other hand, the low mountains are predominantly of calcareous rocks with rendzina and brown soil (Bükk Mts, Aggtelek Mts). The Bükk Mts and Aggtelek Mts are at present a National Park. Natural vegetation: mainly *Quercetum-petraeae-cerris*, submontane oak hornbeam forests, submontane and montane beech forests, e.g., in the Mátra Mts (1015 m), in the Bükk Mts (958 m) and the Zemplén Mts (783 m).

Cochylini species of Hungary

Remarks: the occurrence in Hungary of species in indexed⁷ brackets and square brackets is questionable and further studies are needed. Details are given in the text.

Phtheochroa Stephens, 1829

1. *inopiana* (Haworth, [1811])
2. *schreibersiana* (Frölich, 1828)
3. *pulvillana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])
4. *sodaliana* (Haworth, [1811])
5. *fulvicinctana* (Constant, 1893)
6. *procerana* (Lederer, 1863)
7. [*purana* (Guenée, 1845)]
8. [*duponchelana* (Duponchel, 1843)]
9. *rugosana* (Hübner, [1799])
10. *annae* Huemer, 1990

Hysterophora Obraztsov, 1944

11. *maculosana* (Haworth, [1811])
- = *purgatana* (Treitschke, 1835)

Cochylimorpha Razowski, 1959

12. *hilarana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])
13. *halophilana* (Christoph, 1872)
- = *clavana* (Constant, 1888)
14. *elongana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)
15. [*perfusana* (Guenée, 1845)]
16. *subwolniana* (Danilevsky, 1962)
17. *woliniana* (Schleich, 1868)
18. *obliquana* (Eversmann, 1844)
- = *coenosana* Mann, 1867
19. *jucundana* (Treitschke, 1835)
20. *straminea* (Haworth, [1811])
21. *alternana* (Stephens, 1834)

Phalonidia Le Marchand, 1933

22. *gilvicomana* (Zeller, 1847)
23. *curvistrigana* (Stainton, 1859)
24. *udana* (Guenée, 1845)
25. *manniana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)
26. *affinitana* (Douglas, 1846)
- = *inulana* Constant, 1884
27. *albipalpana* (Zeller, 1847)
28. *contractana* (Zeller, 1847)

Gynnidomorpha Turner, 1916

29. *luridana* (Gregson, 1870)
30. *vectisana* (Humphreys & Westwood, 1845)
- = *griseana* (Haworth, [1811])
31. *minimana* (Caradja, 1916)
32. *permixtana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)
33. *alissima* (Ragonot, 1883)

Agapeta Hübner, 1822

34. *hamana* (Linnaeus, 1758)
35. *largana* (Rebel, 1906)
36. *zoegana* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Fulvoclysia Obraztsov, 194337. *nerminae* Koçak, 1982

= *fulvana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1836)

Eugnosta Hübner, 182538. *lathoniana* (Hübner, [1800])39. *magnificana* (Rebel, 1914)

= *margaritana* (Hübner, [1813])

Prochlidonia Razowski, 196040. *amiantana* (Hübner, [1799])**Eupoecilia** Stephens, 182941. *angustana* (Hübner, [1796–1799])

= *fasciana* (Donovan, 1808)

42. *ambiguella* (Hübner, [1796])43. *sanguisorbana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1856])**Aethes** Billberg, 182044. *hartmanniana* (Clerck, 1759)45. *williana* (Brahm, 1791)

= *zephyrana* Treitschke, 1830

46. *margarotana* (Duponchel, 1836)47. *moribundana* (Staudinger, 1859)48. *nefandana* (Kennel, 1899)49. *margaritana* (Haworth, [1811])

= *dipoltella* (Hübner, [1813])

50. *triangulana* (Treitschke, 1835)

= *kuhlweiniana* Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1836

51. *rutilana* (Hübner, [1817])52. *smeathmanniana* (Fabricius, 1781)53. *tesserana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)54. *sanguinana* (Treitschke, 1830)55. *dilucidana* (Stephens, 1852)56. *flagellana* (Duponchel, 1836)57. *beatricella* (Walsingham, 1898)58. *francillana* (Fabricius, 1794)59. *bilbaensis* (Rössler, 1877)60. *tornella* (Walsingham, 1898)61. *cnicana* (Westwood, 1854)62. *rubigana* (Treitschke, 1830)

= *badiana* sensu Hübner, 1799

63. *kindermanniana* (Treitschke, 1830)**Cochylidia** Obraztsov, 195664. *rupicola* (Curtis, 1834)65. *subroseana* (Haworth, 1811)

= *phaleratana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

66. *richteriana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837)67. *moguntiana* (Rössler, 1864)68. *heydeniana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])69. *implicitana* (Wocke, 1856)

= *coercitana* Staudinger, 1859

Diceratura Djakonov, 192970. *ostrinana* (Guenée, 1845)

= *purpuratana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

Thyraylia Walsingham, 189771. *nana* (Haworth, [1811])**Cochylis** Treitschke, 182972. *roseana* (Haworth, [1811])73. *flaviciliana* (Westwood, 1854)**Longicornutia** Razowski, 196074. *epilinana* Duponchel, 1842**Neocochylis** Razowski, 196075. *hybridella* (Hübner, [1813])

76. [*salebrana* (Mann, 1862)]
 77. *dubitana* (Hübner, [1799])
Cochylichroa Obraztsov & Swatschek, 1958
 78. *atricapitana* (Stephens, 1852)
Brevicornutia Razowski, 1960
 79. *pallidana* Zeller, 1847
Pontoturania Obraztsov, 1943
 80. *posterana* Zeller, 1847
Cryptocochylis Razowski, 1960
 81. *conjunctana* (Mann, 1864)
Falseuncaria Obraztsov & Swatschek, 1958
 81. *degreyana* (Mc. Lachlan, 1869)
 83. *ruficiliana* (Haworth, [1811])
 = *ciliella* (Hübner, 1796)

Biology and distribution of Cochylini in Hungary

Tortricidae

Tortricinae – Cochylini

Phtheochroa Stephens, 1829

The species of this genus cover a vast geographical area, affecting the Holarctic, Neotropical, and Afrotropical regions. According to Razowski (2009), the majority of species are Palearctic and approximately 100 species are known. So far, ten *Phtheochroa* species are known in the Hungarian fauna. Only a few publications have been written on species of the genus (Fazekas 2021). Some species are generally distributed in the country (e.g. *P. schreibersiana*, *P. pulvillana*), but most of them are very rare and local (e.g. *P. annae*) or have disappeared from habitats known in the past.

1. *Phtheochroa inopiana* (Haworth, [1811])

Biology. Bivoltine, the moth flies June-July and August-September. Occupying damp places and woodland edges, Oligophagous species on *Artemisia campestre*, *Eupatorium cannabinum* and *Pulicaria dysenterica*. The overwintering larvae feed inside the roots of food plants.

Habitat. Xero-, and mesophilic meadows and tall herb communities, colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, riverine and swamp woodlands, and wooded pastures. It prefers dolomitic steppe meadows in hilly and mountainous areas but is not common. It is worth looking for on the edges of forests and in shrubby, bushy vegetation, especially on south-facing hillsides and mountainsides.

Text-fig. 3. *Phtheochroa inopiana*

Text-fig. 4. *Phtheochroa schreibersiana*

Range in Hungary. Mainly known locally in the low mountain ranges, mostly in the western part of the country (Transdanubia). It is very scattered in the lowlands (e.g., in Kiskunság and the Tápió protected area).

Distribution. A species with a trans-Palaeartic distribution. It is known from Japan through Central Asia to Asia Minor, west to the British Isles and the Iberian Peninsula. It is fragmented over large geographical areas.

Remarks. A sexually dimorphic species, the females are generally plainer than males.

2. *Phtheochroa schreibersiana* (Frölich, 1828)

Biology. Univoltine, the moth flies from April to early July. The larvae feed on *Prunus padus*, *Populus nigra* and *Ulmus minor* on the leaves to September. Hibernate until the following spring and pupate in early April in the food plant's bark.

Habitat. Lowland oak-hornbeam and closed sand steppe oak woodlands, pannonic oak-hornbeam woodlands, Illyrian beech, and oak-hornbeam woodlands, closed dry deciduous woodlands, forest edges, forest clearings. Less frequently in riverine willow-poplar woodlands.

Range in Hungary. In hilly and mountainous areas; South-Transdanubia, Bakony Mts., Vértes Mts., Mátra and Zemplén Mts. Lowland only in Kiskunság. The pattern of the habitats in Hungary has a more hilly and mountainous character.

Distribution. European, Asia Minor species. Known from the Ural Mountains through the Balkans to Scandinavia, the British Isles in the west, and Spain and Italy in the south.

Remarks. Most of the observations (see the Hungarian Museum of Natural History) are more than 150 years old, and only a few are less than 50 years old.

3. *Phtheochroa pulvillana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

Biology. Univoltine, the adult, flies from May to July, for a long period. The main period of flight culminates between mid-May and mid-June.

Habitat. Margins of hilly and mountainous mesophilous and thermophilous deciduous forests, dry grasslands, grasslands, and pastures. Lowland sand mounds, steppe meadows, saline meadows, planted forest pine forests—agricultural land along roadsides and field margins.

Range in Hungary. In the western and northern parts of the country, it is known for its mid-altitude mountain ranges and hills. In the lowland areas, it has been collected only between the Danube and Tisza rivers (Kiskunság, Tápió region), in the east in the salt marshes of the Hortobágy.

Distribution. A widespread, subspecific, mostly fragmented species in the Palaeartic.

Remarks. The European populations belong to the nomenclatural species described in Germany.

Text-fig. 5. *Phtheochroa pulvillana*

Text-fig. 6. *Phtheochroa sodaliana*

4. *Phtheochroa sodaliana* (Haworth, [1811])

Biology. Univoltine, the adult moths can be found on the wing in May and June and fly just before dusk. The larvae feed on *Rhamnus catharticus* and *Frangula alnus*, spinning the berries together.

Habitat. Mesophilic and xerophilic deciduous forest margins, shrublands, karst scrub forests on hills and mountains; sporadic lowland groves, and secondary (non-native) birch forests on the sand, near streams and watercourses. Hársbokor-hegy, Fót-Somlyó, Jászság (birch forest).

Range in Hungary. Very few sightings are known. It is very local and rare in the mountains around Budapest and the lowlands (e. g. Nagykáta, Kunfehértó) between the Danube and Tisza rivers.

Distribution. It inhabits large areas of the western Palearctic but is absent from North Africa. In the east, it reaches the Caucasus and has even been caught in Kazakhstan. Specimens from Asia need to be reviewed.

Remarks. *Phtheochroa sodaliana* is in some respects reminiscent of a small *P. rugosana* but at once distinguished by the conspicuous ferruginous-red apical spot and the generally white basal area of the forewing. In collections where specimens are slightly worn or fragmented in light traps and have not been genitally examined, this may result in misidentification.

5. *Phtheochroa fulvicinctana* (Constant, 1893)

Biology. The moths fly from June to September, probably in two generations, but this needs further investigation. The larvae feed on *Limonium gmelinii*. This *Limonium gmelinii* ssp. *hungaricum* food plant species are endemic in Hungary, and its native range is Central and Southeast Europe to Siberia and Iran. Further breeding experiments are needed to confirm additional food plants.

Habitat. Mountainous karst scrub forests on dolomitic bedrock, dry sandy and saline grasslands and meadows.

Range in Hungary. Only a few sites are known west of the Danube River (Budai Mts.). Most of the sites are located in the Great Hungarian Plain. Mainly in the sandy areas between the Danube and Tisza rivers, in the east (Tiszántúl region) more locally in the salt marshes, pastures or around salt lakes. The climate of these lowland areas is typically continental. Native wooded heathland survives only in patches.

Distribution. Razowski (2001) does not mention the species in his book on Central Europe, though he does so in his Palearctic volume (Razowski 2009: “S Europe from France to

Text-fig. 7. *Phtheochroa fulvicinctana*

Text-fig. 8. *Phtheochroa procerana*
(Natural posture from the Balkans)

Albania, in more northern territories locally: Switzerland, Romania and Hungary; Dagestan". It is said to be a sub-Mediterranean faunal element, but the actual area affected is significantly larger. For example, in Ukraine, it has been found in Crimea, and Russia along the Volga and in the Caspian lowlands (Sinev et al. 2019). Further chronological studies are needed.

Remarks. *Phtheochroa fulvicinctana*, described from France, is a characteristic species of the Hungarian lowlands; its habitats are mostly within national parks. Population abundance is low.

6. *Phtheochroa procerana* (Lederer, 1863)

Biology. The exact flight times of adults are not known. So far, we have collected specimens only in June and July. The food plant is unknown.

Habitat. To date, only one habitat survives, which can be described as follows: rock grass slope steppe, Buda rabbit-tail grass rock grassland and closed dolomitic rock grassland.

Range in Hungary. Collected only in and around Budapest; just three specimens are known (all in coll. HNHM, Budapest): Budapest, Farkas-völgy, [1]912.VI.20. leg. Uhrík-M. T.; Budafok, [1]918.VII.6. leg. Uhrík-M. T.; Budapest, Sas-hegy, 1942.VI.28. leg. Neugebauer T. We have not seen the species since 1942.

Distribution. According to Razowski (2009), the only occurrence in Europe is Hungary, Romania, and Bulgaria; elsewhere in Asia Minor.

Remarks. The forewings of the Hungarian specimens seen so far have a lighter ground colour than that of the nomino-typical species described from Bulgaria. This is visible in the book by Razowski (2009, Plate 1., Figs 34, 34a). In addition, further differences in habitus can be seen. A comparative study of the Balkan and Hungarian populations should be carried out. Since the species has not been seen since 1942, i.e. for 80 years, the Hungarian population has probably become extinct, and the habitats in Budapest, the Hungarian capital, the sites Budafok (1918) and Farkas-völgy (1912) have been destroyed and built up with houses and roads.

The "Sas-hegy" in Budapest (47°28'56.5 "N 19°01'04.5 "E) is the location of the northernmost geographic occurrence of *Phtheochroa procerana* in Central Europe. The mountain has been studied for 120 years and has been a nature reserve since 1958. This dolomite bedrock mountain is home to the following plant communities: open dolomitic rock grassland (*Seseli leucospermo-Festucetum pallentis*); rock grass slope steppe (*Chrysopogono-Caricetum humilis*); Buda rabbit-tail grass rock grassland (*Seslerietum sadlerianae*); closed dolomitic rock grassland (*Festuco pallenti-Brometum pannonicum*).

The geographic structure of species populations can be understood in terms of two closely related components: 1) population demographic structure and 2) its genetic structure. This method makes it possible to study processes of conservation biological importance such as migration and gene flow, genetic drift and selection, population survival and extinction.

In phylogeographic terms, the analysis of these processes provides an understanding of the structure of the geographical distribution of *Phtheochroa procerana*, its current and evolutionary dynamics and the evolutionary changes that occur during the change in distribution.

Molecular studies could provide insights into where *Phtheochroa procerana* may have been a potential refugium for the species in the Balkans during the last glacial climatic depression and provide answers about the highly isolated occurrence of the species in Hungary. Only studies of this type can answer the questions of fragmentation and isolation.

7. [*Phtheochroa purana* (Guenée, 1845)] – occurrence in Hungary is questionable!

Biology. According to literature, the moth flies in June and July. Probably a monophagous species, larvae have been observed on *Cephalaria leucantha* plants (Swatschek 1958). This plant is present in northern Africa and southern Europe (Albania, former Yugoslavia, Greece, Italy, France, Portugal, and Spain).

Habitat. In the Western Balkans, in the 1980s, I observed it sporadically in xerothermophilous paths and roadsides in disturbed zones, in Mediterranean pine woods edges and shrubland and rocky and karst surfaces.

Range in Hungary. In the Hungarian faunistic literature, the name of the species can only be found in the publications of Gozmány (1968, 1971). Gozmány did not mention any specific locality. During my investigations, I have not found any specimens in any Hungarian collections. Razowski (2009) reported in Hungary, but in his book on Central Europe (Razowski 2001) he does not mention it. In his earlier, Palaearctic volume (Razowski 1970), he mentions Hungary, referring to Kennel (1913). In addition, see Kennel (1921), page 297, where he wrote: "Hab. Südfrankreich, Ungarn, Bithynien":

Distribution. According to Razowski (2009), it is a sub-Mediterranean faunal element, mainly found in southern Europe, France, Croatia, and Bosnia.

Remark. I assume that Kennel's (1913) Hungarian data (specimens) are from the Adriatic coast of historic Hungary, which is now part of Croatia. The found site labels of specimens collected here were always marked "Hungaria". This is probably the reason for the misunderstanding even today. The food plant is planted in gardens, so it cannot be excluded that *Phtheochroa purana* will also appear in Central Europe as an adventive species. Its permanent population in this region is unlikely.

8. [*Phtheochroa duponchelana* (Duponchel, 1843)] – occurrence in Hungary is questionable!

Biology. According to Razowski (2009), the moth flies in two generations from late March to mid-May, and July. The larva and the food plant are not known. It is assumed that it lives on the *Acanthus spinosus* plant. This ornamental plant is native to Mediterranean regions but is planted in many areas as an ornamental.

Habitat. According to the literary sources habitats are unknown. The Hungarian site (Budapest, Csiki-hegy, 314 m) is a degraded dolomite rocky steppe.

Range in Hungary. Only Gozmány (1968, 1971) and Razowski (2009) mention the species from Hungary, without any evidence. We do not yet know the collections where the specimens are kept.

Distribution. Its range is less well understood. It has been collected from the Caucasus region through Asia Minor and Syria to North Africa and is also found in Greece and probably in many areas of the Western Balkans. It is probably a highly fragmented Holomediterranean faunal element.

Remarks. There are no identified specimens in Hungarian collections. There is only one specimen in the Hungarian Museum of Natural History in Budapest, but the locality is not known, no such label exists. It is said to have been collected on the "Csiki" hill (= Csiki-hegy) near Budapest a few decades ago. This area has since been developed and the habitat destroyed.

9. *Phtheochroa rugosana* (Hübner, [1799])

Biology. The moth flies in early May and June. Inactive by day. It may sometimes be seen on warm evenings flying around its habitat but is usually more active towards dusk, occasionally observed at the light. The larvae are oligophagous on flowers and leaves of *Bryonia dioica*, and probably *Echballium elaterium*.

Habitat. Mesophilic and xerophilic meadows, roadsides, weedy areas, and edges of groves. There are also populations in arboreturns (e.g., Szombathely).

Range in Hungary. It is mainly known from low mountainous areas (e.g., Bakony Mts., Mátra Mts., Vértes Mts.) and hills, but it also occurs sporadically on the edges of the Hungarian lowlands (e.g., Tápó-vidék).

Distribution. Its distribution is only partially known. According to Razowski (2009), it is a European faunal element, but this is disputed. According to several literature records (cf. Bradly et al. 1972, Razowski 2009, etc.), it has been found in North Africa, the Canary Islands, Asia Minor, and in Europe from the British Isles through Central Europe to the Balkan Peninsula, it is a local and uncommon species. It is most likely an expansive Holomediterranean faunal element.

Remarks. According to Razowski (2009), images fly in the Palaearctic from April to July.

Such a long flight period is not known in Hungary. Relatively few specimens and literature data are known from Hungary. Most of the identified specimens were collected in the first half of the 20th century, since then there have been very few new observations.

10. *Phtheochroa annae* Huemer, 1990

Biology. Imagines have so far only been collected at night with light in April and May. During the day, they sit on leaves in the vegetation, from where they can be disturbed. The larvae feed on seeds in *Bryonia dioica* fruits but also chew leaves. They pupate in a fine web on the food plant.

Habitat. The habitats studied so far are dominated by forested areas. The species is mainly from the fringes of hornbeam-oak forests, thermophilic oak woods, scrub oak woods and occasionally alder groves, but it has also been collected in loess meadows and sand meadows. Habitat preference needs to be further investigated.

Range in Hungary. The first specimens were collected in Hungary between 1908 and 1915 (Simontornya [Paratype], Nagymaros, Isaszeg, in coll. HNHM, Budapest), but were identified as *P. rugosana*. Later it was found in Nemesgulács and also in the Vértes Mountains (Fazekas 1991, Pastorális & Szeőke 2018). These localities are located in the Transdanubian Mountains at low altitudes (250–300 m).

Distribution. Only a few distribution data are known from Austria, Hungary, Romania, and Greece. The geographical distribution of *P. annae* will only be known if a revision of the species is carried out in collections.

Remarks. Present in very local populations in Hungary, numbers are very low. In some years the species is not even detected.

***Hysterophora* Obraztsov, 1944**

Obraztsov's original description by Razowski (1970) re-described and compared it with *Phtheochroa*. It differs from *Phtheochroa* by the presence of numerous short cornuti, a dorsal groove of the transtilla, and a sclerotized sack of the ductus bursae. According to Razowski, the genus is monotypic, and it shows only slight differences from the *Phtheochroa* genus. The range of genera in the Western part of the Palearctic Region as far Near East, excluded most of the northern area (Razowski 2009).

11. *Hysterophora maculosana* (Haworth, [1811])

= *Cochylis purgatana* (Treitschke, 1835). Type locality: Hungary.

Biology. The moth flies in April and May. The larvae live in flowers of *Chondrilla juncea*, and *Scilia festalis* (this latter is merely an assumption).

Habitat. Dry grasslands, weedy roadsides, abandoned vineyards and orchards.

Text-fig. 9. Wing pattern (left) and male genitalia (right) of *Hysterophora maculosana*

Text-fig. 11. The characteristic wing pattern (right) of *Cochylimorpha hilarana* in the Southern Transdanubia (Hungary); male genitalia (left)

Range in Hungary. Only a few sites are known from Hungary: Gyöngyös (Sár-hegy), Budaörs (Csiki-hegyek), Hévíz, Jászberény, Pécsely, Tihany, Tápió-vidék, Vértes.

Distribution. A Western Palearctic species. It has been observed from pre-Asia and through Asia in Europe to England and Portugal. It was also collected in Crimea (Razowski 2003, 2009).

Remarks. It is very local and rare in this country. No larvae or food plants are known from Hungary.

***Cochylimorpha* Razowski, 1959**

A species-rich genus with a wide geographical distribution in the Palearctic and Oriental regions. According to Razowski (2009): “No constant character separating this genus from *Phtheochroa* is found; in hindwing veins Rs-M1 long-stalked, M3-CuA1 stalked; males without a costal fold; males without any apical process of tegumen should be included in *Cochylimorpha*; exceptionally a reduction of uncus is, however, found in *Phtheochroa* (e.g. in the *P. rugosana* group of species). Other characters are a separation of the arms of vinculum and membranisation of ante ostial sterigma in the majority of *Cochylimorpha*.” In Europe occur 34, and in Hungary 10 species (Fazekas 2022, 2023).

12. *Cochylimorpha hilarana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

Biology. Imago flies in July and August. Food plant: *Artemisia campestris*, monophagous species. According to Szócs (1977), the whitish, dark brown-headed caterpillar forms a 50–60 mm long and 10 mm thick, spindle-shaped, reddish "swelling", a tubercle, in the lower half of the shoot of the food plant.

Habitat. Dry grasslands, saline grasslands, and ruderal meadows.

Range in Hungary Aggtelek karst, Budapest, and surroundings, South Transdanubia, Danube-Tisza area, Szigetköz.

Distribution. From Mongolia, through Central Asia and Asia Minor, to Western Europe and Scandinavia. It is widespread in Central Europe but mostly local; in the Alps, it reaches altitudes of 2000–2200 m.

Remarks. Collections contain specimens collected mainly more than 50 years ago.

13. *Cochylimorpha halophilana* (Christoph, 1872)

= *clavana* (Constant, 1888)

Biology. Imagines were collected mainly from July to early September. Food plant: *Artemisia* spp. According to Buschmann (2004), the caterpillar lives on *Artemisia santonicum*, Razowski (2001) reported *Artemisia gallica* from Central Europe. This latter species does not oc-

cur in our country, only on the western coasts and the Mediterranean coast.

Habitat. Dry grasslands, salty, and sandy grasslands. Huemer (2020) considers it a 'halophyte' species.

Range in Hungary. Few known data: Farnos, Fegyvernek, Jászberény, Kenderes, Király-hegyes, Kisújszállás, Kunmadaras, Nagyiván, Nagykáta, Újszentmargita. All known sites are from the continental Hungarian lowlands. No hilly or mountainous populations.

Distribution. Known from Iran, through Afghanistan, the Volga and Caucasus regions, to south-eastern Europe and Italy.

Remark. Polytypic species; *C. halophilana adriatica* Huemer, 2000 (locus typicus: I-Gorizia), *C. halophilana clavana* (Constant, 1888). The type locality of the nomino-typical subspecies is Russia (Sarepta). The subspecies status of Hungarian populations has not yet been investigated.

14. *Cochylimorpha elongana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)

Biology. Bivoltine species; IV–V and IV–VII. Larva oligophagous: *Achillea millefolium*, *Artemisia campestris*, *A. vulgaris*, *Helichrysum arenarium*. The larvae live in the stems of food plants, hibernate there, and pupate in the spring.

Habitat. Mesophilic meadows, dry grasslands, steppe meadows, rocky grasslands, sandy grasslands, ruderal grasslands; xerotherm species.

Range in Hungary. Budafok, Budaörs (Csiki-hegyek), Budapest (Csillag-hegy, Farkas-völgy, Sas-hegy, Sváb-hegy).

Distribution. Fragmented distribution from Asia Minor through the Balkans to the Urals and in Central Europe to Poland. Localised in Germany (e.g. Saxony; in reclaimed mining areas) and Spain (Andalusia).

Remarks. A species described from Poland (Silesia), it is very local and rare in Hungary, It was collected here only between 1893 and 1958, from late April to mid-July (in coll. HNHM, Budapest). The monitoring of populations is an urgent task. It is questionable whether metapopulations still exist in the agglomeration of Budapest.

15. [*Cochylimorpha perfusana* (Guenée, 1845)] occurrence in Hungary is uncertain.

= *callosana* Herrich-Schäffer, 1851

Biology. According to Razowski (2009), bivoltine; V–VII and VIII. Food plants: *Centaurea stoebe* and *C. triumfettii* (see References).

Habitat. Rocky grasslands, shrublands, steppe meadows, grasslands, dry grasslands, falds, and ruderal meadows.

Range in Hungary. The data reported by Buschmann (2004) (Jászberény, Nagykáta Cseh-domb) were based on unfortunate typos or incorrect determinations.

Distribution. European faunal element: Austria, Croatia, France, Italy, Romania, Switzerland. According to Kovács & Kovács (2005), it has been observed in the Carpathians from 1500 m to 2100 m in xeromontane and humid subalpine meadows. These observations are quite remarkable and suggest a wide ecological plasticity.

Remarks. Its occurrence in Hungary was reported by Gozmány (1968, 1971) as "*callosana* HS.", as a result, the post-millennial nomenclatures indicated it, but no *perfusana* specimens are in museums. Apart from the above-mentioned lists, only Buschmann (2004) has so far published it in connection with the collection of the Mátra Museum. The specimens deposited there according to Buschmann (Jászberény and Nagykáta Cseh-domb) were misidentified: After revision, they were specimens of *C. straminea* (rev. & det. Buschmann). There is no positive evidence of the species occurrence in Hungary.

16. *Cochylimorpha subwolniana* (Danilevsky, 1962)

Biology. The food plants and developmental stages of the caterpillars are still unknown. The species' flight period is from late April to mid-July.

Habitat. In Romania (Kovács & Kovács 2004), the species was observed on dry steppe-like slopes in sandy areas. Specimens from Bélmegyer were collected in a boggy area by grass netting in the early twilight, moths did not fly to light in the evening (Tokár 2015).

Range in Hungary. Bélmegyer, Fáspuszta, 2014.V.9, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Gp. ♂ 12193, ♀ 12245 ZT), Zdenko Tokár leg. & coll.

Distribution. Disjunct distribution from western China through Central Asia and Romania to Hungary. In the eastern part of the country, it reaches its westernmost limit of geographical distribution in the „Tiszántúl” region.

Remark. The highly isolated Central European populations of the species described from Kazakhstan are only partially known, further research is needed.

17. *Cochylimorpha woliniana* (Schleich, 1868)

Biology. Univoltine; VI–VIII. Specimens from early May have also been found in Hungary. May flight is not yet known in the literature of the Palaearctic. Larvae live on *Artemisia absinthium* from August then overwinter.

Habitat. Dry meadows, fallows, grasslands, ruderal grasslands; usually on sandy soils, but also sporadically on calcareous, volcanic rocky grasslands and sloping steppes (Fazekas 2018).

Range in Hungary. So far, only a very local population is known in the area of Lake Balaton and Lake Velence: Kis-Balaton (Zalavári-erdő), Tihany, Csopak, Agárd (Fazekas 1993, 2018, Petrich 2001, Szabóky 1982).

Distribution. Mainly known from southern and Central Europe, very local European fauna element (Razowski 2009). However, based on studies by Nupponen et al. (2001), the species has been found from Europe to Mongolia. On this basis, the classification of Razowski as a European faunal element is highly questionable; it is rather a Siberian faunal element.

Remarks. The distribution and bionomics of the species populations in the entire Pannonian biogeographical region should be reviewed. As the habitats now discovered are predominantly in the Balaton-Highlands National Park, it would be important to initiate a monitoring study.

18. *Cochylimorpha obliquana* (Eversmann, 1844)

= *coenosana* Mann, 1867

Biology. Bivoltine species: V–VI; VII–IX. Food plants: *Artemisia maritima*, *A. stepposa* (Razowski 2001, 2009), *A. santonicum* is a possible food plant in Hungary. The larvae live in the roots, hibernate there, and pupate in the spring.

Habitat. Dry sandy meadows and salt marshes.

Range in Hungary. The Sopron Hills, Kisalföld, Mezőföld, the Danube plain, and the Jászság, a local and rare species east of the Tisza River. Evidence of sites: Alattyán, Biatorbágy, Budaörs, Csorna, Dinnyés, Dömsöd, Fegyvernek, Gyoma, Kenderes, Kunmadaras, Mikepércs, Nadap, Nagyiván, Nagykáta, Pákozd, Sárkeresztúr, Sopron, Sukoró, Szeged, Szigetszentmiklós, Újszentmargita, Velence.

Distribution. Known from Mongolia through southern Siberia and Central Asia to Hungary and western Austria.

Remarks. The western area border is the Lake Fertő region (Burgenland). Only old observation data are available in this fluctuation zone. In the Hungarian context, it is questionable whether there is significant gene flow in the set of connected local populations (metapopulations).

19. *Cochylimorpha jucundana* (Treitschke, 1835)

Biology. Univoltine; VI–VIII. Its food plant is probably one of the *Artemisia* species.

Habitat. It can be collected day and night (by light) in dry, south-exposed rocky grasslands, and mountain meadows, and scrub up to 1000 m altitude (Balkans).

Range in Hungary. Only two specimens are known from the country (14-15.VI.1937. Pécs, leg. Klimesch J.; in coll. Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, and the Natural History Museum in Vienna).

Distribution. From the Bashkir Country in southern Russia, the Balkans, the Pannonian Basin and northern Italy to Spain, France, and Belgium, but is local and rare everywhere. The Belgian occurrence is probably based on misidentification.

Remarks. There are no known sightings in Hungary in the last 85 years.

20. *Cochylimorpha straminea* (Haworth, [1811])

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VII, VIII–X. The larvae live on *Artemisia*, *Centaurea*, *Chrysanthemum* and *Scabiosa*; in the stem below the flower heads. They also consume seeds and young shoots. The second-generation overwinters as a very small larva and feeds on the stems of new shoots in spring.

Habitat. Mainly inhabits lowland and hilly xerotherm forest edges, scrub, rocky grasslands, steppe slopes, meadows, pastures, mown grasslands, roadsides, field margins or fallow land.

Range in Hungary. Widespread in the country and one of the most common species of euryoecious *Cochylimorpha*. The mapping of the sites clearly shows that no data are available from very significant geographical areas.

Distribution. Widespread and locally common in the Western Palearctic.

Remarks. According to Ferenc Buschmann (pers. comm.), *C. straminea* specimens from the sandy habitats of Jászság are lighter in colour, and the mid-wing brown band is rarely accompanied by dark scales, so they can easily be confused with *C. perfusana* (Guenée, 1845).

21. *Cochylimorpha alternana* (Stephens, 1834)

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–VI., VII–IX. The larvae live in the flower heads of *Centaurea scabi-osa*, which are still closed, feeding on the flowers and the immature fruits. Second-generation larvae overwinter in the early stages.

Habitat. Dry grasslands, pastures, sandhills, dolomitic and limestone rocky meadows, sloping steppe mosaics.

Range in Hungary. Collected sporadically in many geographical regions of the country (Mecsek Mts, Mezőföld, Transdanubian Mts, Szigetköz, Danube–Tisza area). Typical sites: Agárd, Agasegyháza, Albertirsa, Bánhida, Budafok, Budaörs, Dinnyés, Fót, Hosszúhetény, Isaszeg, Kárász, Komló, Magyarereggy, Nagymaros, Pécsvárad, Tarhos, Verőce.

Distribution. From Iran through Central Asia to Scandinavia, the British Isles, North Africa in the south and the Middle East. According to Razowski (2009), it is a European faunal element, but this is unlikely; it is more probably a multicentric Western Palearctic faunal element (Fazekas 1994).

Remarks. The forage plant *Centaurea scabiosa* is widespread throughout Europe, except in the Mediterranean and in the northern landscapes. It reaches eastwards to Lake Baikal in eastern Siberia and is also established in Eastern Asia, North America, Australia, and New Zealand, so the appearance of *Cochylimorpha alternana* in other continents may be expected.

Phalonidia Le Marchand, 1933

The geographical distribution of the genus is wide. Known from the Holarctic, Oriental, and Neotropical regions. Eight species are known from Europe, 6 of which have a wider distribution. Seven species have been identified in Hungary. The larvae live mainly on Asteraceae plants, mostly oligo- or polyphagous.

Razowski has analysed the taxonomy of the genus in detail in several works. Most recently, Razowski (2009) indicated that *Phalonidia* is closest to *Gynnidomorpha*, but *Phalonidia* differs in the shape and position of the socii complex which is not perpendicular to the tegumen; the flat, not dorsally upward-turned base of costa of valva; and the shape of median part of the transtilla. In *Phalonidia* and *Gynnidomorpha* a circle of spines is present in the corpus bursae (See Razowski 2011).

22. *Phalonidia gilvicomana* (Zeller, 1847)

Biology. Univoltine; VI–VIII. The larvae live in the seeds and stems of *Chenopodium* spp., *Lampsana communis*, *Mycelis muralis*, *Prenanthes purpurea* and *Solidago virgaurea*.

Habitat. Scrub, forest clearings, forest edges, dry and mesophilic meadows. Volcanic, calcareous and dolomitic areas. No observations from the lowland regions yet.

Text-fig. 12. *Phalonidia gilvicomana*;
wing pattern (left), male genitalia
(right) (the uncus and saccus
magnified)

Range in Hungary. I collected the species in Hungary for the first time on 15.VIII.1989 in the southern part of the country, in the Mecsek Mountains (Komló), at an altitude of 350 m in a clearing of an oak forest (see Fazekas 1994). This site is an intensively used urban and coal-mining area, with buildings and domestic gardens, which have been inhabited for centuries. The specimen flew at night to the light of a 160-watt mercury vapour lamp. It has recently been found in several mountainous areas of the country: Börzsöny Mts., Bükk Mts., Mátra Mts., Sopron Mts., Transdanubian Mts. (Bakony, Pilis), Zemplén Mts.

Distribution. Previous research has observed it only in Europe, from western Russia to northern Scandinavia, western France, and the British Isles.

Remarks. The first male specimen in Hungary was identified by genital examination (Fazekas 1994, fig. 7). I collected it with the light source in the same place continuously until 2015, but no new specimen was observed.

23. *Phalonidia curvistrigana* (Stainton, 1859)

Biology. A few specimens were collected in Hungary only in June and August. Larvae and food plants have not yet been encountered in this country; various literatures refer to *Solidago virgaurea*.

Habitat. Saline meadows in the lowlands, and mesophilic meadows in the mountains.

Range in Hungary Only two lowland sites (Jászberény, Kompolt) and one mountain site (Zemplén Mts.; Telkibánya) are known.

Distribution. Trans-Palaeartic species with disjunct.

Remarks. Studies in Hungary are scarce, with few precise observations.

24. *Phalonidia udana* (Guenée, 1845)

Biology. According to Mutanen et al. (2012), the larva of *P. udana* lives in stems of *Lysimachia thyrsoiflora* and *L. vulgaris*, which are not close relatives to *Mentha* or *Lycopus*, the known food plants of *P. manniana*. Both food plants, however, inhabit moist meadows. It is thus likely that where their ranges overlap, *P. manniana* and *P. udana* may co-occur in the same habitats. The larva of *P. udana* makes a ca. 15–20 cm long gallery, usually in the lower part of the stem of the food plant but does not enter the rootstock. The larva overwinters full-grown in the upper part of the gallery but does not make a visible emergence hole. The larvae seem to prefer relatively thick stalks in *L. thyrsoiflora*. Two larval galleries have been observed in one stem.

Habitat. Wet meadow, marshy landscape.

Range in Hungary. Only one very old Hungarian specimen is known: East Hungary, Bátorliget, 25.VII.1949, leg L. Kovács, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas (in coll. HMNH, Budapest) (see Fazekas 2014). The food plant *Lysimachia vulgaris* is common in Hungarian groves and marshes, high meadows, reed beds and wet meadows, where populations of the species can be found.

Distribution. The species is known from Europe (Denmark, Finland, Germany, France, Hungary, Latvia, Norway, and Slovakia) although one dissected specimen from Central Siberia (Novosibirsk) shows close affinity to that taxon as well.

Remarks. The taxonomic separation of the *Ph. manniana* and *Ph. udana* species has long been a matter of debate. Razowski, in his 2009 book Palaeartic, even considers it synonymous with *Ph. manniana*. Mutanen and colleagues have examined in detail the biology and genetic differences between the species pairs, and both taxa are now considered valid species (see Mutanen al. 2012).

25. *Phalonidia manniana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–VI., VII–VIII. Larvae live in stems on *Menta*, *Alisma*, *Botomus*, *Lycopus* and *Inula* spp.

Habitat. Near waterfronts, in marshy areas, wet meadows, alder forests, rarely in lowland sand hills, planted pine and poplar forests.

Range in Hungary. It prefers Hungarian lowland and hilly landscapes. It is widespread, but localised and rare in places.

Distribution. From Manchuria through Siberia and Central Asia to the British Isles. It also occurs sporadically in the Iberian Peninsula and Asia Minor.

Remarks. The majority of Hungarian metapopulations are highly fragmented.

26. *Phalonidia affinitana* (Douglas, 1846)

= *inulana* Constant, 1884

Biology. Bivoltine: V–VI., VII–VIII. Larvae live in stems and flowers on *Aster tripolium*.

Habitat. It prefers dry and saline meadows or pastures, mostly in lowland areas. It has also been observed near the shores of lakes and reed beds. It also occurs sporadically on the edges of mesophile woodland or in the forest of pines with the sandy hills of the Hungarian lowlands.

Range in Hungary. In Hungary, it is a typical species of continental lowland saline habitats.

Distribution. Widespread from the Urals and Caucasus to Western Europe, but its exact areas are still to be investigated.

Remark. It has not yet been observed in mid-altitude mountains.

27. *Phalonidia albipalpata* (Zeller, 1847)

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VI., VII–VIII. (>IX.). Larva monophagous on *Limonium gmelinii* (Willd.) Knutze subsp. *hungaricum* (Klokov) Soó.

Habitat. Lowland dry saline heaths, grasslands, sandy oak woodland clearings and their fringe zone, are also observed in forest pine forests planted between sand hills.

Range in Hungary. Occurs mainly in the lowland region between the Danube and Tisza rivers, with scattered occurrences east of the Tisza. West of the Danube River (Mezőföld): very local and rare.

Distribution. From the Altai mountains through the southern parts of Central Europe to Italy and Corsica, but is also found in Asia Minor.

Remarks. According to Razowski (2009) „Habitat not known.” Hungarian observations correct this finding. *Limonium gmelinii* subsp. *hungaricum* is an endemic plant of the Hungarian wormy salt marshes, with a focus on the Danube plain and east of the Tisza River.

28. *Phalonidia contractana* (Zeller, 1847)

Biology. Bivoltine V–VI, VII–IX. Larvae are polyphagous in flowers, stems,

and seeds on *Artemisia*, *Anthemis*, *Cichorium*, *Inula* and *Lactuca* plants.

Habitat. Euryecious species, observed in dry, warm lowland habitats, moist, cool mountain valleys, birch woodland, cranberry association complexes, marshy landscapes, alder woodlands, abandoned orchards, vineyards, rocky mountain karst scrub.

Range in Hungary. It is widespread, but mostly in flat rural areas, reaching altitudes of up to 1000 m in the northern mountains.

Distribution. Widespread in the Palaearctic, from Kashmir to the Iberian Peninsula.

Remarks. The boundaries of the species' distribution need to be further explored.

Gynnidomorpha Turner, 1916

According to RAZOWSKI (2011), *Gynnidomorpha* is very closely related to *Phalonidia*, but *Gynnidomorpha* can be distinguished by the following characteristics: the presence of a sclerotized fold between the socii, the costal part of the valva distinctly turned upward dorsally at the base, the socii almost perpendicular to the tegumen, and the end of the median part of the transtilla which is very long, terminating in a pair of minute tips. The presence of the circle of spines in corpus bursae is a putative synapomorphy shared by *Phalonidia* and *Gynnidomorpha*. The genus's areas of distribution are usually very wide. Found in all biogeographic regions, but the area of focus is the Palaearctic (9 species). There are 6 species in Europe and 5 in Hungary.

29. *Gynnidomorpha luridana* (Gregson, 1870)

Biology Bivoltine; V–VI, VII–VIII. According to Razowski (2001, 2002, 2009), the food plant is *Matricaria recutita*. Some authors dispute this, preferring the nutrient plant *Odontites vernus*. There are no known Hungarian studies on this.

Habitat. It has been observed in arid and mesophilic grasslands, reclaimed coal mine sites, meadows, and pastures (hills and mountains) near streams, abandoned vineyards and thickets, and rocky steppe meadows.

Range in Hungary. A highly localised and rare species in remote regions of the country: Budapest, Gyöngyös, Komló, Mánfa, Nagykáta, Szentpéterföldre.

Distribution. Many parts of the Palaearctic, from Japan to Korea and north-east China to the Russian Far East. It is known in Asia Minor, in Europe from Scandinavia to the British Isles, and as far south as Corsica.

Remarks. The bionomics and abundance of Hungarian populations are poorly known.

30. *Gynnidomorpha vectisana* (Humphreys & Westwood, 1845)

= *griseana* (Haworth, [1811])

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VI, VII–IX. Larvae are polyphagous on *Plantago*, *Triglochin* and *Salicornia* plants; flowerheads are eaten.

Habitat. mainly wet saline meadows, marshlands, and wet meadows along hillside streams.

Range in Hungary. Locally rare in the region between the Duna and Tisza rivers. To the

Text-figs 13-14. Wing pattern of *Gynnidomorpha luridana* (13) and *Gynnidomorpha vectisana* (14)

south are the Mecsek Mts, and to the west the marshes of Lake Balaton.

Distribution. From China transcontinentally to the British Isles and in south Italian regions.

Remarks. Only a few, highly isolated, low populations are known in the Hungary.

31. *Gynnidomorpha minimana* (Caradja, 1916)

Biology. Probably a two-generation species; V–?, VII–VIII. Larva lives in seed capsules of *Pedicularis palustris*. This food plant is local and rare in Hungary (Bartha & Király 2015). Botanists consider it to be “disappearing”.

Habitat. In marshy meadows and wet pastures.

Range in Hungary. Only lowland observations are known; Bátorliget, Szentmártonkáta. Bátorliget is a famous “ancient bog” in Hungary. Its survival dates back to the early postglacial period. This is a nature reserve, all three specimens were collected in 1948 and 1949, and since then there have been no further sightings from this area. A previously unknown population was found 195 km west of the old site in 2009 at Szentmártonkáta. This is a saline grassland, a typical vegetation: *Festuco pseudovinae artemisiosum*. This plant community is a representative of the Central Asian salt marshes of the Carpathian Basin, the most typical and widespread habitat of the Hungarian Great Plain.

Distribution. Known sporadically from Japan through central Eurasia to the British Isles.

Remarks. There are surprisingly few authentic records from Hungary. It is probably a “relict” species from the postglacial period that is in regression.

32. *Gynnidomorpha permixtana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VI; VII–VIII. Larva is polyphagous in stems, seeds, and flowers of *Alectrolophus*, *Alisma*, *Butomus*, *Euphrasia*, *Gentiana* and *Solidago*.

Habitat. In lowland sandy oak woodlands, steppe meadows, hill country wet and boggy meadows, mown meadows, pastures, village gardens, planted pine woods etc. Euryecous species.

Range in Hungary. Widespread but local and rather uncommon in Southwest Hungary and the Great Hungarian Plain.

Distribution. Trans-Palaeartic distribution, from Japan to Western Europe.

Remarks. There have been few bionomic studies in Hungary so far.

33. *Gynnidomorpha alismana* (Ragonot, 1883)

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VII, VIII–IX. Probably a monophagous species whose larvae live in the stems of the *Alismana plantago-aquatica* food plant.

Habitat. Prefers wet, moist areas of the plains.

Range in Hungary. It is a locally occurring and uncommon species, mainly in the central and eastern lowlands of the country. Very few observations have been made west of the Danube River (= Transdanubia). It has not yet been found in the mid-altitude mountain ranges. This is interesting because in Hungary it is the mountain research that is the most intensive.

Distribution. It is a bicentric species, with its range centred in Europe, but there are also known sightings in China (see Razowski 2009).

Remarks. According to my observations, the species is in strong regression in Hungary. Damaged, worn *G. alismana* specimens can only be distinguished from the very similar *G. vectisana* species by genital examination.

Agapeta Hübner, [1825]

Species from the central and western parts of the Palaeartic region. Three species are found in Hungary. Among them, *Agapeta largana* (Rebel, 1906) stands out in terms of fauna history. Razowski (2009, 2011) indicated that *Agapeta* is closely related to *Ceratoxanthia*; short transtilla. The two genera share with *Fulvoclysia* a yellow forewing colour. *Agapeta* differs from *Ceratoxanthia* by its small socii, simple sacculus, strong sclerites of the basal region of the disc of the valve, and the presence of a distal process of the juxta. All known species have a large sterigma and lack sclerites of the corpus bursae, the only exception being *Agapeta zoe-gana*.

Text-fig. 15. Male genitalia of *Agapeta hamana* (detailed description in the text)

34. *Agapeta hamana* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Biology. The moths fly continuously from May to the end of October; bivoltine species. The larva feeds on *Carduus*, *Cirsium*, *Ononis* and *Trifolium* plants.

Habitat. Euryecous species, on dry and mesophilic meadows, fields, fallows, roadsides, pastures, reapers, on lowland sands, and the edge of alder forests. In the northern mountains, it reaches altitudes of up to 1000 m.

Range in Hungary. It is widespread throughout the country, but nowhere common.

Distribution. They populate vast areas of Asia and Europe. According to Razowski (2009) a European–Altai–Turanian zoogeographical element.

Remarks. The species' area centre is unclear.

35. *Agapeta largana* (Rebel, 1906)

Biology. Univoltine species; VI–VIII. The larvae probably live in the roots of *Carduus* species. This observation is not confirmed.

Habitat. Lowland dry steppe meadows, grasslands, forest pine forests planted between sand hills, remnant relict oak woodland clearings and edge zones.

Range in Hungary. A much rarer and more localised species than the previous species. It is found only in the central lowland saline landscapes of the country.

Distribution. It lives in a small geographical area in Western Austria, Hungary, Romania, and Greece.

Remarks. It is an especially important species from a faunal point of view. The exact genealogy is not known.

36. *Agapeta zoegana* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Biology. Flight period; VI–VIII. (sometimes until the middle of September). The larva feeds on the roots of *Centaurea*, *Jurinea* and *Scabiosa* plants.

Habitat. Meadows, pastures, grasslands, reedbeds, forest margins, rocky grasslands, karst scrub, sand pine forests, wet riparian forests, and marshlands (euryecous species).

Range in Hungary. It is widespread and locally common in all natural geographic areas.

Distribution. From Central Asia to the British Isles, Scandinavia, and Asia Minor.

Text-figs 16-17. Wing pattern of *Fulvoclysia nerminae* (16) and male genitalia (17)

Remarks. One of the most common Cochylini species in Hungary.

Fulvoclysia Obraztsov, 1943

One species occurs in Hungary and Europe. According to Razowski (2009, 2011) *Fulvoclysia* is like *Agapeta* and *Ceratoxanthia*. The male genitalia of *Fulvoclysia* differs in the presence of spiny areas of valva and small aedeagus that tapers distally just beyond the zone (Fig. 17).

37. *Fulvoclysia nerminae* Koçak, 1982

= *fulvana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1836) nec ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Biology. Moths have been collected in VI–VIII. Larva feeds on *Scabiosa* spp. food plants (in stem and root).

Habitat. Hilly and mountain meadows, pastures up to an altitude of 1000 m.

Range in Hungary. It is known only in the north, in the Mátra and Bükk mountain ranges.

Distribution. European species, there are old observations from Asia Minor, but these data have to be confirmed. This species may have its northernmost distribution limit in the Luxembourg Moselle valley (Hellers 2002). According to Pröse et al. (2003), the species is "threatened with extinction" in Bavaria.

Remarks. Knowledge of Hungarian populations is incomplete.

Eugnosta Hübner, 1825

Thirteen species are known in the Palaearctic, four in Europe, and two in Hungary. The Palaearctic species are mostly characterized by silvery forewing ground colour. According to Razowski (2009, 2011) *Eugnosta* is closely related to *Commophila* and *Prochlidonia* and is comparable to *Eupoecilia* and some tropical genera. Most of the Palaearctic species of *Eugnosta* are easily distinguished by the lustrous forewing ground colour. The male genitalia is distinguished by large, well-sclerotized socii; female genitalia is like those in several other genera. Males of *Commophila* differ only slightly from *Eugnosta*, and the two genera may prove synonymous. *Prochlidonia* differs from *Eugnosta* only in the shape and size of the caulis.

38. *Eugnosta lathoniana* (Hübner, [1799–1800])

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VI; from VII to early IX. Larvae live on *Carduus hamulosus*.

Habitat. Dry grasslands, pastures, fallows, dolomitic and limestone rocky grasslands, karstic forest margins, dry forest clearings. Occurs from the lowlands up to 700 m in the mountains. In Asia Minor (Karaman, Merkez, det. et photo: Ö. Koçak) and the Iberian Peninsula (leg. et det.: F. Graf), it reaches altitudes of 1000–1200 m.

Range in Hungary. Few occurrences in the Transdanubian region and the North-Hungarian Mountains, fragmented localities in the Danube–Tisza Interfluvium in central Hungary.

Text-fig. 18. Wing pattern of *Eugnosta lathoniana*: the species are mostly characterized by silvery forewing ground colour.

Distribution. A western Palaearctic species. Occurs from the Urals, through the Caucasus, in Asia Minor, Central and Southern Europe, west to Portugal, and in North Africa. Local, sometimes fragmented populations are known everywhere. Sinev (2019) catalogues the species as having an extremely limited distribution in Russia.

Remarks. In Hungary, most of the sites are known from the Budapest (capital) agglomeration. These are mostly old observations, 50–100 years old and most of the recorded places have been built up or completely transformed and have disappeared. The species is highly localized and in regression in the country. Populations may survive only in protected areas, for example in Natura 2000 sites or protected landscape areas.

39. *Eugnosta magnificana* (Rebel, 1914)

= *margaritana* (Hübner, [1813])

Biology. Univoltine; V–VI. Larvae and food plants are not known.

Habitat. Most of the known and very old habitats in Hungary are in Budapest. A significant part of them has been destroyed, built up and can no longer be reconstructed. Only one relatively natural habitat has survived – in the nature conservation area: Sas-hegy.

The "Buda Sas-hegy Nature Reserve" belongs to the Danube-Ipoly National Park. The 30-acre (120,000 m²) area on the top of the hill (257 m) was placed under protection in 1958. It was one of the first nature reserves in Hungary, protecting the limestone landscape and its special flora and fauna. Sas-hegy is a small dolomite hill, the steep dolomite slopes are covered with the original vegetation of dolomite grassland, dominated by *Festuca pallens* and *Carex humilis* (Zólyomi 1958). Probable habitats of occurrence of this species should be sought: closed rock grassland; endemic grassland of *Seslerietum sadlerianae*; dry open rock grassland on steep southern slope (*Seseli leucospermi-Festucetum pallentis*); mosaic grassland, shrubs around; large grassy area on a moderate eastern slope. According to Bölöni et al. (2011) typical habitats are calcareous open rocky grasslands, closed rocky grasslands, and calcareous rocky steppes (Fazekas 2022).

Range in Hungary. Budafok [1904], Budapest [1877] (Kamaraerdő, Káposztásmegyér [1936], Sas-hegy [1893], Széchenyi-hegy [1903], Újpest [1903]), Pápa (1892). The first sighting in Hungary was in 1877 and the last in 1936. Consequently, it seems that nobody has collected or photographed it in Hungary in the 88 years since.

Distribution. Southern and partly Central Europe, Russia (Central part of the European Russia, Crimea, Don region, Volga region, South Ural), Armenia, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Transcaspian area, Iran, Central Asia, Afghanistan, China: Inner Mongolia (Rebel 1914; Ra-

zowski 1970, 2002, 2009; Kuznetsov 1978; Budashkin 2009; Budashkin & Richter 2021, Sinev et al. 2019).

Remarks. *Eugnosta magnificana* is likely to be extinct in Hungary. It is neither listed in the Hungarian Red Book nor the national list of protected species; it has escaped the attention of Hungarian conservation authorities and Lepidoptera researchers.

Prochlidonia Razowski, 1960

Two species are known in the West Palaearctic. Razowski (1987, 2011) compared *Prochlidonia* with *Eugnosta* and *Commophila*. According to Razowski (2009b), *Prochlidonia* is closely related to *Eugnosta*, as evidenced by the shape of socii, but in *Prochlidonia* the caulis is very large, expanding at the end ventrally. Characters of *Prochlidonia* are rather similar to those of *Eugnosta* and may prove to be of specific importance only. Supposed autapomorphies of *Prochlidonia* are the shape and size of the caulis and the dorsolateral lobes of the juxta.

40. *Prochlidonia amiantana* (Hübner, [1799])

Biology. Univoltine; V–VI. According to Razowski (2001), there are two generations in Central Europe, but this was not confirmed by Hungarian observations. The early stages are not known.

Habitat. 150–350 m altitude, mainly in mountainous mesophilic and xerophilic meadows, and karst scrub.

Range in Hungary. Most of the sites are in the Budapest agglomeration (Farkasrét, Farkas-völgy, Lipótmező, Sváb-hegy, Szamárrét), which has been inhabited since ancient times, with vineyards and gardens from the Middle Ages onwards, and then increasingly built-up from the 18th century onwards. Additional local and highly isolated sites: Csákvár, Gyöngyös Hollóháza.

Distribution. So far, it is known only from Europe. It has been found from Romania through the Pannonian region and the Balkans to southern France, but is highly fragmented.

Remarks. According to Kovács & Kovács (2006) in Romania, the larvae are most likely to live on *Helianthemum* species (Cistaceae). Adults fly in two generations. The species is characteristic of open, dry biotopes. From Romania it has been reported only from the Apuseni Mountains, Colții Trascăului. There is no continuity between the Hungarian and Romanian populations, with a geographical distance of more than 300 km. In my opinion, the species is in regression and endangered; conservation measures are justified. Monitoring studies should be carried out in national parks and nature reserves.

Eupoecilia Stephens, 1829

Species of the genus are mainly found in the Palaearctic, Oriental and Australian regions. There are 4 species in Europe and 3 in Hungary. *Eupoecilia* is closely related to *Eugnosta* and its allies, but *Eupoecilia* is easily distinguished by having a dorso-basal lobe of the socius and a wreathlike arrangement of the distal cornuti.

41. *Eupoecilia angustana* (Hübner, [1796–1799])

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VII; VII–IX. The larvae are polyphagous and feed in flowers, leaves, and seeds of *Achillea*, *Calluna*, *Origanum*, *Plantago*, *Solidago*, and *Thymus* spp.

Habitat. In a wide variety of ecological conditions: in bush habitats, hill and mountain meadows, pastures, orchards, forest clearings, deciduous and pine woodland edge zones, along roadsides, and agricultural fields.

Range in Hungary. It has been observed in almost all regions of the country. It seems to prefer mountainous and hilly areas.

Distribution. From Japan, through temperate and meridional Russian areas, to the British Isles.

Remark. It is one of the most distinctive Cochylini species in Hungary, but population abundance is not known.

Text-figs 19-20. Comparison of the wing pattern: 19. *Prochlidonia amiantana*, low variability; 20. *Eupoecilia angustana*

42. *Eupoecilia ambiguella* (Hübner, [1796])

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–V; VII. The polyphagous larvae live on *Acer campestre*, *Cornus* spp., *Clematis vitalba*, *Frangula alnus*, *Hedera helix*, *Lonicera xylosteum*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Prunus* spp., *Ribes* spp., *Rubus* spp, *Sambucus racemosa*, *Vitis vitifera* etc.

Habitat. Dry and mesophilic oak woodlands, sunny rocky woodland communities, wooded lowland steppe woodlands, rocky grassland communities, marginal scrub, cottage crofts, and vineyards.

Range in Hungary. Throughout the country, but very localised, mostly in hilly and mountainous areas.

Distribution. In the temperate and meridional vegetation zones of Eurasia, from Japan to the Iberian Peninsula.

Remark. Appears to be a widespread species in Hungary, but the life history and abundance of fragmented populations are poorly known.

43. *Eupoecilia sanguisorbana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1856])

Biology. Flight times; VI–VII., VIII, possibly having two generations. According to references the larvae live on *Sanguisorba officinalis*; in seedheads and flowers.

Habitat. So far there are no credible observations in Hungary. The plant lives in marshy, boggy meadows. A widespread in the western and central parts of the country and the north-east (see Bartha & Király 2015).

Range in Hungary. Surprisingly few, very local populations are known from the following sites: Bakonybél (mountain area place); Farnos, Nagykáta and Tápióság (lowland populations).

Distribution. A highly fragmented species was detected from China (Heilongjiang Province), through Kazakhstan to France and Belgium.

Remarks. In the Pannonian biogeographical region, it is a species in a strong regression and should be monitored as soon as possible, especially in protected areas. Since the larvae feed in flower heads, the timing of mowing should be carefully regulated.

Aethes Billberg, 1820

Species are characteristic of Neotropical, Oriental, and Holarctic regions. According to literature, 70–75 species are known in the Palearctic region and are more widespread in the western Palearctic. Several endemic species are known in Central Asia. There are 45 European species, of which 22 are found in Hungary.

The wingspan of the image is 8–23 mm, markings, and colouration are very variable. In the forewing, all veins separate or R4-R5 stalked, chords, M-stem and CuP atrophied; in

Text-fig. 21. Venation and forewing pattern of *Aethes* genus (after Fazekas 2008)

hindwing Rs-M, stalked, rearing veins run separate. In *Aethes*, the assumed basic pattern consists of basal, dorso-post basal, median and subterminal fasciae, and a tornal marking. Several of the species are polymorphic and have distinct ecological forms. Ecological variation, such as that found in *Ae. hartmanniana*, *Ae. rutilana* and *Ae. kindemanniana*, also appears to have been intensively studied. There are several groups of closely related taxa occasionally treated as valid species or, formerly, subspecies or groups of species or infraspecific taxa (e.g. *Ae. hartmanniana/piercei* and *Ae. cnicana/rubigana*).

The hindwing is usually more or less unicolorous, sometimes with darker suffusion. Usually, the ground colour is brownish grey or grey, cilia paler than wing or creamy, whitish.

Recorded foodplants are mainly species of Asteraceae (Compositae). The larva lives in various parts of plants, often in stems and roots; it hibernates and pupates in spring or early summer. The moths fly from April to September and maybe uni-, bi- and multivoltine.

Razowski (1994, 2011) recognized that *Aethes* and *Aethesoides* are closely related, sharing two synapomorphies: the presence of slender, curved socii from a broad, hairy base and the rod-like sclerite coupling the tegumen with the valve. According to Razowski (2009b), the two genera have a similar thread-like distal part of the socii, but *Aethes* has a more generalized valva.

44. *Aethes hartmanniana* (Clerck, 1759)

[*piercei* auct.]

Biology. Bivoltine. The moth flies from mid-May to mid-June and from early July to mid-August. Oligophagous. Recorded foodplants are *Scabiosa ochroleuca*, *S. columbaria*, *Succisa pratensis* and *Knautia arvensis*. The larva lives in the rootstock.

Habitat. Moist-rich fens, eu- and mesotrophic meadows, Colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths. Rare and local in the marshy country. Sporadic in halophilic and dry open grasslands. Altitude from 90 m to 600 m (Fazekas 2008).

Range in Hungary. Widespread in the western and northern parts of Hungary. Frequent on the hills and in mountains of medium height and avoiding the dry habitats on the plains.

Distribution. From the Ural Mountains and the Caucasus to Britain. According to Kennel (1913) in Armenia and Asia Minor.

Remarks. A rather variable species: some very dark specimens occur in water-fringing herbaceous communities. *Ae. hartmanniana* and *Ae. piercei* occur sympatrically in the West

Text-fig. 22. *Aethes hartmanniana*; the variability of male and female genitalia in Hungary based on samples from different populations (after Fazekas 2008).

Hungarian Borderland (FAZEKAS 1992). Further study is needed to improve knowledge about taxonomy and distribution areas. For Hungarian morphology and biology see Fazekas (1992).

45. *Aethes williana* (Brahm, 1791)

Biology. The moth flies in two generations from April to mid-September. Larva polyphagous, on *Daucus carota*, *Eryngium campestre*, *Gnaphalium sylvaticum* and *Helichrysum arenarium*; full-grown larva 9–10 mm long, body yellowish; pupa straw coloured, 6–7 mm long, the cocoon light brown. In Hungary, the larva is injurious to cultivated carrots (Farkas 1969). Not uncommonly, a quarter of the crop can be destroyed. Two years are sometimes spent in the pupal stage.

Habitat. Xerotherphilous species, found mainly in the closed loess and sand steppes, saline pasture, and edge of agricultural land. Altitude from 90 m to 650 m (e.g. Mátra Mts).

Range in Hungary. Very local in the Great Hungarian Plain, and sporadically in some habitats of the mountains at medium altitude (for example Bükk and Mátra Mts).

Distribution. From Mongolia to North-West Africa and Western Europe. Chorotype; centralasiatic-europeo-mediterranean.

Remarks. *Ae. williana* is often a pest in plantations of carrots, especially in certain years when it becomes abundant.

46. *Aethes margarotana* (Duponchel, 1836)

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–V.; VII–VIII. The monophagous larva lives in roots and

stems of *Eryngium campestre*, instead of *Eryngium maritimum* which does not occur in Hungary. Hibernation in larval stage.

Habitat. Sand steppes, lowland dry degraded grasslands, slope steppes, dry and semi-dry closed grasslands (for example Bakony and Mecsek Mts.). Altitude from 100 m to 400 m.

Range in Hungary. Sporadic occurrence in lowlands and lower mountain regions.

Distribution. From the Amur region through Eurasia (in the temperate and meridional vegetation zones) to western Europe and North Africa.

Remarks. Not recorded from Eastern Hungary (Tiszántúl Region), except for the Nyírség region. Monitoring of the populations around Budapest based on 50-100 years old observations seems to be futile.

47. *Aethes moribundana* (Staudinger, 1859)

Biology. Bivoltine, flying in late May to mid-June and from July to August. According to Budashkin (1993), the larvae feed in generative parts of flowers of *Sideritis taurica*; each larva utilises 4 or 5 flowers. *Sideritis taurica* does not occur in the Pannonian region, and in Hungary the larval food plant is unknown. *Sideritis montana* does, however, occur in this area.

Habitat. Dry, rocky grassland with scrub (Pákozd: Kanca-hegy).

Range in Hungary. It is very localised and rare; Bükk Mountains, Isaszeg, Pákozd, Simontornya.

Distribution. From China to Mongolia, through Central Asia and North Africa, but is fragmented.

Remarks. *Ae. moribundana* is very rare and local in Hungary but could be overlooked and therefore careful search is required.

48. *Aethes nefandana* (Kennel, 1899)

Biology. From the dates of collections of adults; V–VI; and VII. Possibly a two-generation species. The biology of the larva is not described; it may live in the stem of *Eryngium* spp.

Habitat. Mainly in lowland dry, sandy grasslands, pastures, pine forests planted on sand, but also known in mountain rocky habitats (xerothermic grasslands, karstic shrub forests, etc.).

Range in Hungary. It has been observed mainly in the sandy regions between the Danube and Tisza rivers. It is much rarer in some mountainous regions (Budai Mts., the foothills of the Mátra Mts.).

Distribution. A local species occurring in Central Asia, Asia Minor and through the Balkans to Central Europe.

Remarks. The Hungarian populations are in the so-called fluctuation zone of the species' western range limit. It is probably a "relict" species of a post-glacial dry warm period that is in regression. Endangered.

49. *Aethes margaritana* (Haworth, [1811])

Biology. Moths fly in one generation; VI–VIII. The larvae are polyphagous on seeds and flowers of *Achillea*, *Chrysanthemum*, *Matricaria* and *Tanacetum* food plants.

Habitat. Xerophilous and mesophile meadows, grasslands, pastures, forest margins and clearings, rocky grasslands, karst scrub forests, no longer cultivated hilly vineyards and orchards, village gardens, etc.

Range in Hungary. Prefers the hilly and mountainous areas west of the Danube (Transdanubia Regions) and the northern mountains. It is exceedingly rare and local in lowland areas.

Distribution. Widespread from Central Asia to the British Isles. The centre of its area is Europe.

Remarks. The adults have been collected in Hungary up to the altitude of 1000 m.

50. *Aethes triangulana* (Treitschke, 1835)

Biology. Moths fly in two generations; IV–VI; VII–VIII. According to the literature sources, the food plant is *Pseudolysimachion [Veronica] longifolium*.

Habitat. Ecologically quite different edge habitats; marshes, rich fens, eu- and mesotrophic meadows and tall herb communities, water-fringing, and fen tall herb communities, colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, open sand steppes, dry and semi-dry closed grasslands, riverine and swamp woodlands etc.

Range in Hungary. Sporadically in mountainous and hilly areas; Mátra, Mecsek, Budai, Bükk Mts (up to 1000 m), Gödöllő Hills. Highly fragmented populations in lowland regions; Hajdúság, Nyírség, Berettyó-Körös region, Danube plain, Tápió region. Further expected areas of occurrence: the Dráva river basin and the western Hungarian border region as well as the area around Lake Balaton, etc.

Distribution. Temperate and meridional vegetation zones of Eurasia, from the Amur to the Iberian Peninsula.

Remarks. Knowledge of Hungarian populations is still incomplete.

51. *Aethes rutilana* (Hübner, [1817])

Biology. The moths have been collected in one generation: V–VII. Larva lives in spun leaves of *Juniperus communis*.

Habitat. Sandy lowland areas, hilly and mountainous barren meadows, and sheep pastures.

Range in Hungary. Sporadically in the central lowland area of the country, exceptionally in some mountainous areas (Buda Hills, Mecsek Hills).

Distribution. From Siberia, through Finland, to central Europe and the Iberian Peninsula. In the European mountains, it reaches altitudes of 2300–2500 m. *Aethes rutilana* was introduced into British Columbia sometime before 1965.

Remarks. There are remarkably few known sites in Hungary. Endangered (proposed as a future Hungarian Red Data Book species).

52. *Aethes smeathmanniana* (Fabricius, 1781)

Biology. Adults fly in one generation; IV–VI. There is also a second generation in the literature, but this has not yet been observed in Hungary. Larva oligophagous on Asteraceae species; *Achillea millefolium*, *Anthemis cotula*, *A. arvensis*, *Centaurea nigra* and *Lactuca sativa*.

Habitat. Hygrophilous and mesophile meadows, road verges, weed communities, field margins, forest edges, sandy and saline lowland grasslands, arboretums, karstic woodlands, rocky grasslands (in mountain areas), village gardens and garden sheds.

Range in Hungary. A widespread and locally common species in many parts of the country. In the north, it reaches altitudes up to 1000 m in the mountains.

Distribution. Widely distributed Holarctic species. In the Nearctic region, this species has been recorded in Canada (Alberta, British Columbia, Quebec, Yukon Territory) and the United States (California, Maine, Minnesota, Montana, Ohio, and New Jersey). See <https://en.wikipedia.org>

Remark. This is one of the most widespread euryecious species of Cochylini taxa in Hungary.

53. *Aethes tesserana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VI. VII–VIII. Larvae are oligophagous in the roots of *Pieris* and *Hieracium spp.*

Habitat. Xerophilous and mesophilous meadows, pastures, grasslands, coppices, forest margins, rocky grasslands, karst scrub forests, and sloping steppes.

Range in Hungary. Widespread mainly in lowland regions, more localised in hilly and mountainous areas. It has been found on plains in the steppe zone, but also in mountain ranges up to 1000 m above sea level.

Distribution. Mostly considered to be a European species. According to Razowski (2009),

the data from Iran require confirmation.

Remarks. Monochrome, brownish specimens are also rare.

54. *Aethes sanguinana* (Treitschke, 1830)

Biology. The moths' collection time; VI–IX. According to Razowski (2001) in Central Europe; V–VI, VII–VIII. I assume that in Hungary one-generation populations spread over a long period. Larva monophagous in stems of *Eryngium campestre*.

Habitat. Closed loess and sand steppes, dry grasslands, pastures, roadsides, rocky hillsides with karst scrub, thermophilous woodland fringes, calcareous open rock grasslands, village crags, ruderal areas, etc.

Range in Hungary. Rare and local species, mainly on the continental plains of the Danube–Tisza Interfluve, highly isolated in some mountain areas (around Budapest, Mecsek-Mts, and Villány Hills near the southern border).

Distribution. Known in Asia Minor, from the South Urals region through Central Europe to North Africa. It prefers the sub-Mediterranean regions.

Remarks. There is also an old collection record from the southern edge of Lake Balaton (Fonyód), but the exact location of the population is not known.

55. *Aethes dilucidana* (Stephens, 1852)

Biology. So far, a total of 5 collected specimens are known from the end of July 1952, since then no sighting data are available. According to literature reports, the larva lives on *Peucedanum sativum*, *Pastinaca sativa*, and *Heracleum sphondylium* (Razowski 2009).

Habitat. Xerophilous and mesophilous meadows, pastures, forest edges.

Range in Hungary. Only one old, much-studied site near Budapest: Ócsa.

Distribution. Razowski (2001) mentioned only Austria and the Czech Republic in his book on Central Europe. He was not aware of its occurrence in Hungary. The species occurs from southern Siberia through Europe to North Africa.

Remark. The species has disappeared from Hungary, and it is also possible that it has become extinct. The only Hungarian site is a unique, 3575-hectare glacial bog remnant. The Ócsa Landscape Protection Area belongs to the Danube–Ipoly National Park.

56. *Aethes flagellana* (Duponchel, 1836)

Biology. The adults emerge in May and fly until August. They may form two generations, but this has not been confirmed by exact studies. The larvae live in stems and flowers of *Eryngium campestre*.

Habitat. Closed loess and sand steppes, dry grasslands, pastures, roadsides, rocky hillsides with karst scrub, thermophilous woodland fringes, calcareous open rock grasslands, village crags, ruderal areas, etc.

Range in Hungary. Mainly in the western and northern hills and mountains of the country, and in the Danube–Tisza Interfluve.

Distribution. From Iran to Central Asia and Asia Minor, it has been observed in many parts of Europe.

Remark. Widespread in Hungary, but population abundance is moderate.

57. *Aethes beatricella* (Walsingham, 1898)

Biology. Two adults were collected in Hungary: 1974.VI.27. and 1976.VI.29. The larva lives on *Conium maculatum* and *Smyrniolum olusatrum* (Razowski 2009).

Habitat. Salt meadows, closed loess and sand steppes, edges of the road.

Range in Hungary. Only two known sites in the Hungarian Plain; Nagyiván–Darvas, Kunfehértó.

Distribution. Known from Central Asia through Europe to North Africa.

Remarks. Possibly an endangered species in Hungary, our knowledge is incomplete.

58. *Aethes francillana* (Fabricius, 1794)

Biology. The moths were collected from June to September, representing probably two generations of the species. The larvae are polyphagous in seeds or flowers of *Angelica*, *Astydamia*, *Crithmum*, *Daucus*, *Eryngium*, *Ferula*, *Pastinaca*, *Peucedanum*, and *Petroselinum* plants.

Habitat. Varied, mainly lowland steppe meadows, grasslands, sporadically wet, marshy landscapes.

Range in Hungary. Highly fragmented in several regions of the country: Budafok, Csepel, Jászberény, Kunpeszér, Nagykőrös, Nyírbátor, Vörs.

Distribution. Known from Central Asia through Europe to North Africa and the Canary Islands.

Remarks. No observations from the extensive hilly areas and higher mountains.

59. *Aethes bilbaensis* (Rössler, 1877)

Biology. The moth fly in VI–VIII. The larvae oligophagous on *Carum verticillatum* and [*Crithmum maritimum*] the latter plant is not native to Hungary.

Habitat. Wet and boggy meadows, lowland steppe meadows, grasslands, hilly and upland mesophilic meadows, grasslands, oak woodland edge zone, rocky sunny hillsides. It was also cultivated in village gardens (PL. Kárász, Komló; Mecsek Mountains). The ecological spectrum is broad.

Range in Hungary. Local and rare, preferring hills and mountains (up to 1000 m). It has not yet been found in the eastern part of the country.

Distribution. Known from Iran through Central and Asia Minor to Europe and North Africa. A fragmented West Palaearctic species.

60. *Aethes tornella* (Walsingham, 1898)

Biology. Moths were collected from June to early August. The larva and food plant are unknown in Hungary.

Habitat. Collected in a wide variety of habitats, preferring meadows, pastures and grasslands, and the marginal zone of mesophilic and hygrophilic forests.

Range in Hungary. Local and rare in the lowlands and lower mountain regions (up to 300–400 m).

Distribution. Known from Central Asia through Asia Minor and the Middle East to the British Isles and the Iberian Peninsula.

Remark. There are no suitable ecological corridors and stepping stones between highly fragmented populations. They have no reproductive biological link. Habitat connectivity has been eliminated by agricultural land.

61. *Aethes cnicana* (Westwood, 1854)

Biology. One generation yearly: V–VII. The larvae are oligophagous on *Carduus* species. The eggs are laid in the cup leaves of the flowers. Pupae are in dead stems of food plants.

Habitat. Wet meadows, and reedbeds, along streams in tall fescue communities, in the fringe zone of alder forests, and mountain and hilly stream valleys. It sometimes flies in village gardens (e.g. Mecsek Mts).

Range in Hungary. Local and rare mainly in the south-west of the country (hilly areas). Isolated in the north in the Bükk Mts.

Distribution- A so-called Trans-Palaearctic species, known from East Asia through Asia Minor to Western Europe.

Remark. There are only a few specimens in Hungarian collections.

62. *Aethes rubigana* (Treitschke, 1830)

= *badiana* sensu Hübner, 1799

Biology. Moths collected from June to September. The exact generational boundaries are not known, probably a two generational species. The larvae oligophagous on *Arctium lappa*, and *A. tomentosum*.

Habitat. Mainly in hilly and upland meadows, pastures, grasslands, woodland margins, rocky grasslands, and karst scrub, but also found in lowland alkaline steppe meadows.

Range in Hungary. Widespread, not uncommon species; prevails in many sites, from the slopes of the northern mountains up to 100 m altitude.

Distribution. In the Palaearctic is widely known from Japan, East Russia, China, and Mongolia to Western Europe.

Remarks. One of the most widespread *Aethes* species in Hungary.

63. *Aethes kindermanniana* (Treitschke, 1830)

Biology. There are few data from Hungary. Adults were collected from May to early September. According to Razowski (2009), there are two generations: V–VI, VII–VIII. The larvae live in flowers of *Artemisia campestris*, and *Tanacetum corybosum*.

Habitat. Xerophilous and mesophilous grasslands, ruderal areas (few observations).

Range in Hungary. In mountain and hill areas; Transdanubian Mountains and Mecsek Mountains, Villány Hills. In lowland areas; south Transdanubia, Kiskunság, Nyírség.

Distribution. Central and western Palaearctic species.

Remarks. Most observations are 50–100 years old, with few new data.

Cochylidia Obraztsov, 1956

Six species are known to occur in Hungary and Europe. Razowski (2002) compared *Cochylidia* to *Diceratura* and listed two putative synapomorphies: according to the structure of the valve and the elaborate distal part of the corpus bursae.

64. *Cochylidia rupicola* (Curtis, 1834)

Biology. There are few flight data from Hungary. They were collected from May to June. The larvae live in the flowers and the seeds of food plants: *Eupatorium cannabinum*, *Galatella linostris*, and *Lycopus europaeus*.

Habitat. Marshes, riverine willow-poplar woodlands, water-fringing and fen tall herb communities, rocky grasslands, and steppe meadows. It can also be collected by light in dry forest edges, forest clearings and forest paths. There seem to be two ecological forms.

Range in Hungary. Very localised and rare: in Transdanubia, North-Hungarian Mountains, sporadically in the lowland (Jászfelsőgyörgy, Szentmártonkátá).

Distribution. Occurs only in the West-mid-Palaearctic; from Asia Minor, through European Russia to Western Europe.

Remarks. According to some authors, the species' lifestyle is entirely water dependent. This is not confirmed by observations of populations far from wetlands.

65. *Cochylidia subroseana* (Haworth, 1811)

= *phaleratana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

Biology. The adults fly from June to August (Razowski 2001, 2002, 2009). According to Hancock et al. (2015: 72) completely commit themselves to *Solidago virgaurea* as the oviposition plant. They write about the caterpillar: "Headlight to dark brown. Body deep yellow. August - May; feeds from August on the flowers and unripe seeds. living in the flowers and retarding their development; when full-grown, in late September or early October, leaves the flowerhead and hibernates in a cocoon among ground debris."

Habitat. Mesophilic and hygrophilic meadows, grasslands, and forest edges.

Range in Hungary. Two specimens from eastern Hungary; Nyírbátor [Bátorliget] (see Fazekas 1994: in coll. Natural History Museum Vienna) Kaposvár 1948. V. 31., 1949. VII. 16. (2), 1951. V. 7., 30., VII. 14.

Distribution. Known from Japan to the British Isles.

Remarks. Some of the published Hungarian data are uncertain and should be revised (Szabóky 1994b, Ács & Szabóky 1993). There are no specimens in Hungarian state collections. Some private collections are not accessible. Old specimens (1948, 1949 and 1951) from South Transdanubia (Kaposvár) are preserved in the Janus Pannonius Museum (Pécs). The labels show dates in May and July (see Szabóky 1982). I have not seen the specimens; the curators have not allowed me to examine the collection.

Text-figs 23-24. Wing pattern of *Cochylidia rupicola* (23) and *Cochylidia subroseana* (24); variability is low in size of markings and colouring.

66. *Cochylidia richteriana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837)

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–V, VI–VIII. The larvae live in flowers and roots on *Achillea millefolium* and *Artemisia campestris* (see References).

Habitat. The only authentic site is the peripheral zone of a resort town (Dombóvár-Gunarasfürdő), near the Kapos River with wet meadows, ploughs, and small tree lines and small woods.

Range in Hungary. In Hungarian literature, only Fazekas & Schreurs (2010) have so far published a report on Dombóvár (South Transdanubia). This isolated site is quite remarkable.

Distribution. A trans-Eurasian species with a huge range.

Remarks. The collection of the Hungarian Museum of Natural History contains specimens from the 19th century, but the original labels are missing and we do not know where the specimens were collected.

67. *Cochylidia moguntiana* (Rössler, 1864)

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–VI, VII–IX. Larva monophagous in stems *Artemisia campestris*.

Habitat. Various in colline and montane hay meadows, acidic grasslands and heaths, Halophytic habitats, dry open grasslands, white oak scrub woodlands, thermophilous woodland fringes, semi-natural vegetation of abandoned vineyards and orchards etc.

Range in Hungary. Small populations are scattered in lowlands and hilly areas.

Distribution. Trans-Palaeartic species through southern Siberia and central Asia to western Europe.

Remarks. The accumulation area of its distribution in Hungary is sandy and calcareous regions.

68. *Cochylidia heydeniana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–VI, VII–IX. Larva lives on *Conyza canadensis*, *Erigeron acer* and *Solidago virgaurea*.

Habitat. Occur in very different places, such as mountain meadows, and pastures, near lowland bogs, in the bush grasslands of the continental lowlands, and near the forested heaths of the coal mine areas.

Range in Hungary. It is a highly localised and rare species in many regions of the country.

Distribution. A trans-Palaeartic species was reported from as far away as Japan and the British Isles.

Remark. In the northern mountains, it reaches altitudes of up to 1000 m.

69. *Cochylidia implicitana* (Wocke, 1856)

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–VI, VII–IX. It is difficult to separate the generations in time. The larvae are polyphagous in flowers and seeds; of *Alchemilla*, *Aster*, *Anthemis*, *Helichrysum*, *Matricaria*, *Solidago* plants etc.

Habitat. Arid, mesophilic, and hydrophilic plant communities, continental sandy wastelands, coal mine recultivation areas, village gardens, hillsides, abandoned vineyards, etc.

Range in Hungary. Mainly found in lowland and hilly regions but is not known in higher mountain areas.

Distribution. Found in many places from Central Asia to Scandinavia and Northwest Africa.

Remarks. One of the most widespread *Cochylidia* species in Hungary.

Diceratura Djakonov, 1929

The species of the genus are mostly found in the western Palaearctic region. The species are distributed from Iran through Kazakhstan to Western Europe. In Europe, nine species are recorded. Only one species lives in Hungary. Razowski (2002, 2011) compared *Diceratura* to *Cochylimorpha*, treating it as more advanced, owing to its specialized distal part of the tegumen and its strongly reduced socii. According to Razowski (2009b), *Diceratura* is closely related to *Cochylidia*, but *Diceratura* lacks minute spines at the end of the costal part of the valva. The female genitalia areas are like those of *Cochylidia*.

70. *Diceratura ostrinana* (Guenée, 1845)

= *purpuratana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

Biology: Moths fly in two generations from May to the end of August. The larvae feed on flowers of *Dipsacus fullonum* and *Chondrilla juncea*.

Habitat. Composition is varied; dry and mesophilic meadows, wet sites near streams and lakes, pine plant communities in sandy areas, south-facing rocky grasslands and karst scrub, orchards in village gardens, and reclaimed areas of coal mines.

Range in Hungary. Few observations are localised mostly in hilly and mountainous areas (up to 1000 m); on the plains only occasionally found.

Distribution. Found from southern Siberia through Central and Asia Minor to North Africa. In Central Europe, it is found only in Austria, Hungary, and Slovakia (Razowski 2001). More recently found in Belgium, Germany, and Luxembourg (de Prins 2016, Werno 2014).

Remark. The geographical distribution of the species is poorly known.

Text-figs 25-26. *Diceratura ostrinana*; 25. wing pattern, 26. male genitalia, aedeagus on the left, valva on the right.

Thyraylia Walsingham, 1897

This genus name has not been used by authors in Hungarian literature.

Diagnosis of the adult. Labial palps are well developed, the second segment much broadened in its subterminal part, third segment short. Antennae reach to the mid forewing. The forewing is long and narrow, and the costal margin at the base of the wing is slightly bent, otherwise, it is straight, and the tip of the wing is short. The outer margin is convex. All veins are independent, chords, median and CuP veins missing. Rib R5 ends on the costal margin before the wing tip. Nerve CuA2 originates between nerves R1 and R2. The background colour is yellowish white. The brown or greyish pattern of different shades consists of a basal patch or a patch in the basal third of the costal margin; a median transverse band, which is fragmented; and a subapical transverse band. The fringes are light yellow.

Genitalia of male: The tegumen is short and wide, well sclerotized. Uncus outlined. Socii are small, weakly sclerotized. The vinculum is well-sclerotized, and its ventral branches are not fused. Valva is narrow, elongated and distally narrowed, with a concave costal margin, with pointed tip, sacculus with a long, pointed terminal apophysis. Transtilla with the sharp median part. Juxta is simple, and flat, with a rounded ventral margin.

Genitalia of females: The anal papillae are normally shaped and short. The anterior and posterior apophyses are short. Tergite VIII is short. The sternum is weakly sclerotized. Antrum narrows and weakly sclerotized. Bursa copulatrix has ductus bursae and corpus bursae membranosus, without signum.

The genus is the most widespread in the Nearctic with 7 described species. In Europe and Hungary, only one species with a Holarctic distribution is known (Razowski 2009).

71. *Thyraylia nana* (Haworth, [1811])

Biology. Univoltine: V–VIII. The larva is monophagous on *Betula* spp.

Habitat. Occur in sandy, calcareous, and volcanic landscapes, where the food plants live. Mostly collected by light at the edges of forests.

Range in Hungary. A local and rare species in the country; Southern Transdanubia, Kisalföld, Mezőföld, Naszály-Mountains, North-Hungarian Mountains (Mátra, Bükk, Zemplén-Mountains), in the Hungarian Great Plain it is highly isolated (Tápió-region).

Distribution. Holarctic species: it is widespread in Europe but local everywhere.

Remarks. The problem of the genus name has already been addressed by Razowski (2009: 100 p.) in his book Palaeartic. The species *Cochylis nana* was transferred to the genus *Thyraylia* in a recently published American study (Metzler & Brown 2014) and this status was confirmed with genetic studies by Brown et al. (2020: 167).

Text-figs 27-28. *Thyraylia nana* 27. wing pattern, 28. male genitalia, aedeagus on the left, valva on the right.

Text-figs 29-30. Differences in the wing pattern of similar *Cochylis* species; 29. *C. roseana*, dorsum of forewing of some specimens with pink intermixture; 30. *C. flaviciliana*, only in the intensity of the pink colouring of the forewing.

***Cochylis* Treitschke, 1829**

The genus is distributed in the Holarctic, Oriental, and Neotropical regions. In Europe, 14 species were found, 9 in Hungary. Larvae are oligophagous and feed mainly on plants belonging to Asteraceae. There are one or two generations annually, and overwintering occurs in the larval stage. Razowski (2002, 2011) compared *Cochylis* with *Diceratura* and *Cochylidia* and several New World genera and mentioned only supposed synapomorphy – the cone-shaped cluster of cornuti. According to Razowski (2009b), *Cochylis* is similar and probably allied to *Cochylidia* and *Diceratura*, but *Cochylis* has a highly specialized *socii* complex. The female genitalia resemble those of *Cochylidia* and *Diceratura*, but those of *Cochylis* have a more distinct membranous sack extending from the distal part of the corpus bursae.

72. *Cochylis roseana* (Haworth, [1811])

Biology. Adults fly in a single generation; VI–VIII. The larvae live in seed heads and flowers of *Aster*, *Antirrhinum*, *Solidago*, and *Dipsacus*.

Habitat. Dry, warm hill and mountainside grasslands, karst bush forests, or mesophile meadows, but appear in village gardens and even in arboretums (for example, Pécs).

Range in Hungary. Local occurrences on medium-altitude mountain ranges and in a few localities on the hills. Sporadic observations in the northern region of the Hungarian Plain.

Distribution. It has been observed in fragments from China (Gransu region) to Iran and Asia Minor. In Europe, it has been recorded from the Ural Mountains to the British Isles.

Remarks. A few observations are known in Hungary. Abundance in populations is low.

73. *Cochylis flaviciliana* (Westwood, 1854)

Biology. The moth was collected in May and from June to August. According to Razowski (2009) there are two generations yearly. The larvae live in *Knautia arvensis* and *Scabiosa ochroleuca*.

Habitat. Mainly dry and mesophilic meadows, pastures, mowed fields, less frequent village gardens, hygrophilic meadows near rivers, and agricultural mosaics.

Range in Hungary. A very local and rare species; Dombóvár, Dudar, Kárász, Mohora.

Distribution. Eurasian element which, according to our data, is distributed in Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Russia, Belarus, Ukraine, Estonia, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Slovakia, Switzerland, Germany, Holland, Great Britain, Ireland, Luxembourg, France and Italy, Slovakia, Switzerland, Germany, the Netherlands, Great Britain, Ireland, Luxembourg, France and Italy, the islands of Sardinia and Sicily, Czech Republic, Austria, Hungary and Balkan re-

gions (after References).

Remarks. I first described it as a new species in the Hungarian fauna 33 years ago (Fazekas 1991), and later published it again with a Dutch colleague (Fazekas & Schreurs 2010). The species is remarkably rare in central Europe. In neighbouring Romania, it was collected only at altitudes of 1550–1750 m (Kovács & Kovács 2020).

***Longicornutia* Razowski 1960**

In the earlier period, this genus name was not used in Hungarian literature. This genus name has only been in use since 2020 (Kovács & Kovács 2020). For more information, see the following.

Diagnosis of the adult. Labial palps are well developed, the second segment is much broadened in its subterminal part, and the third segment is short. Antennae reach the mid-forewing. The forewing is broad and elongated, the costal margin at the base of the wing concave and otherwise straight, wing tip is short. The outer margin is convex. All ribs are independent, rib R5 ends on the costal margin before the wing tip. Chorda, median and CuP vein missing. The hindwing is slightly wider than the forewing, apex prominent and pointed. Sc+R1 rib is long, exceeding half the length of the costal margin. All nerves are independent.

Genitalia of the male: tegumen large, well sclerotized. The uncus is missing. Socii exceedingly small, and poorly sclerotized. The vinculum is strong, and its ventral branches are broader, not fused. Valva has a long concave costa, narrow rounded tip, long sacculus, broad in basal half and has a sharp terminal apophysis. Juxta has a pair of short apophyses. Aedeagus long and narrow, terminal apophysis long, narrow, bent and pointed, vesica with an exceptionally long, thick, bent and pointed cornutea.

Genitalia of the female: anal papillae short. Anterior and posterior apices short. Segment VIII is short. Tergite is narrow and weakly sclerotized. Antrum lat. Bursa copulatrix has ductus bursae broad and well sclerotized, with large sclerites and corpus bursae membranous, without signum.

The genus is widespread in the western Palearctic region (Razowski 2009).

Text-figs 31-32. *Longicornutia epilinana*; 31. wing pattern, 32. male genitalia (aedeagus on the left, valva on the right). The valva has a long concave costa, the aedeagus long and narrow, terminal apophysis long, narrow, bent and pointed.

74. *Longicornutia epilinana* Duponchel, 1842

Biology. Bivoltine: IV–VI; VII–VIII. Sporadic specimens occur in September but have also been observed in the first week of October. The phenology requires a more detailed study. The larvae are polyphagous in seeds of *Cephalaria*, *Linum* and *Solidago* plants.

Habitat. Diverse, xerophilic, mesophilic and hygrophilic meadows, forest edges, rocky grasslands, karst scrub, ruderal areas, etc.

Range in Hungary. Mainly in the western part of the country (Transdanubia), where it is also mostly found in the lower regions of the hills and mountains. Sporadically observed in the lowlands and the North Hungarian Mountains.

Distribution. From the Russian Far East through Central and Asia Minor to Europe and North Africa.

Remarks. The recent genus classification of this species is not clear to me (see Kovács & Kovács 2020). The authors have written: “Consequently, despite appearances, *Longicornutia* is a genus specifically created to fit the species *Cochylis epilinana*. We now reinstate *Longicornutia* Razowski, 1960, stat. rev. as a valid genus with *Longicornutia epilinana* (Duponchel, 1842) comb. rev. as a type species. We are not aware of any other species that could be placed in the genus *Longicornutia* and consider the genus to be monotypic. Razowski (1960: 314) placed *Longicornutia* just before the genus *Cochylis*. Brown et al. (2020: 167 fig. 7, 171) state: ‘In the barcode tree (fig. 7) [*Cochylis epilinana* Duponchel] it occupies a sister position to *Cochylis* s.s. In our opinion, Razowski’s concept is now fully confirmed with recent genetic studies”. (Originally written in Romanian, own translation into English.)

Neocochylis Razowski, 1960

Diagnosis of adults. The forewing is short and narrow, the costal margin at the base of the wing is slightly bent and otherwise convex, the wing tip is short. The outer margin is convex. All veins are independent, chorda, median and CuP veins missing. Rib R5 ends on the costal margin before the wing tip. Nerve CuA2 originates between nerves R1 and R2. The background colour is yellowish-white or light yellow. The brown, greyish or light brown pattern of different shades consists of a basal spot (in *N. dubitana*) or small spots at the base of the costal margin, a fragmented median transverse band and a subapical transverse band. The fringes are light yellow.

Genitalia of male: The tegumen is short and wide, well sclerotized. The uncus is missing. Socii are small and poorly sclerotized. The vinculum is strong, its ventral branches are not fused. Valva is broad and widening distally, with a narrow-rounded tip, sacculus is relatively short with a basal (*N. salebrana*, *N. hybridella*) or subterminal (*N. dubitana*) apophysis. The transtilla has narrow sides and a thickened median part. Juxta has a pair of apophyses. The aedeagus is narrow and long, bent below the pointed terminal apophysis, vesica with a cluster of small spinules. The caulis are short.

Genitalia of females: The anal papillae are normally shaped and short. The anterior and posterior apophyses are short. The tergite VIII is long. The sterigma is broad and weakly sclerotized, enveloping the antrum. Bursa copulatrix has ductus bursae and corpus bursae membranous, without signum.

The genus is widespread in the Palaearctic region, but *N. dubitana* has a Holarctic distribution. In the Palaearctic and Europe, it is represented by 5 species, 3 of which have been reported from Hungary.

75. *Neocochylis hybridella* (Hübner, [1813])

Biology. Adults fly in April–August. According to observations in Hungary, the most important oviposition plant is certainly *Picris hieracioides*. Other important food plants are the *Crepis* species.

Habitat. Various types of meadows, pastures, rocky grasslands, sloping steppes, ruderal areas, weedy swamps in clay and coal beds, arboretums, village gardens, planted pine woodlands of sandy lowlands etc.

Range in Hungary. Mostly observed on hills and mountains (up to 1000 m). It occurs

Text-figs 33-34. *Neocochylys hybridella*; 33. wing pattern, 34. male genitalia (aedeagus on the left, valva on the right).

sporadically in steppe areas of the lowlands with a strongly continental climate.

Distribution. Widespread in the Palearctic (Razowski 2009).

Remark. Based on genetic analyses, Brown and colleagues (2019) segregated the species from the genus *Cochylis* and proposed a new genus named *Neocochylys*.

76. [*Neocochylys salebrana* (Mann, 1862)] – A controversial species in Hungary.

First mentioned by Kennel (1913) from Hungary. Much later, Gozmány & Szabóky (1986) reported a specimen collected in Kiskunság. In the 10,000 years since the ice age, Kiskunság has been a semi-desert steppe with rolling sand hills. It is a Natura 2000 site of high conservation value with several relict species of plants or animals. I do not exclude the presence of *N. salebrana* species. It is not known from any other country in Central Europe (Razowski 2001). Recorded from the Caucasus Region, Asia Minor, Balkan (Bulgaria Macedonia and Romania), Italy and France. Although there are literary records from Hungary, no one has ever seen the proof. Therefore, it is not yet considered a member of the Hungarian fauna.

77. *Neocochylys dubitana* (Hübner, [1799])

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VI, VII–VIII. Rarely, they are seen even in September. The larvae are polyphagous in flowers and seedheads of food plants: *Arctium*, *Carduus*, *Centaurea*, *Cirsium*, *Crepis*, *Hieracium*, *Picris* and *Solidago*.

Habitat. Xerophilous and mesophilous grasslands, reedbeds, pastures, woodland edges, forest roads and clearings, rocky steppes, karst scrub, village gardens, stream banks, abandoned vineyards and thickets etc.

Range in Hungary. Locally observed in hilly and mountainous areas up to 1000 m. Very rare in lowland areas, in bush meadows and salt meadows.

Distribution. Holarctic species.

Remarks. Few observations have been made so far.

***Cochylichroa* Obraztsov & Swatschek, 1958**

This genus name has not been used by the authors in the Hungarian literature, so the diagnosis of the genus is given below. For further, detailed information see Brown (2019).

Diagnosis of Adults. Labial palps are well developed, the second segment much broadened in its subterminal part, third segment short. Antennae reach to the mid forewing. The forewing is short and narrow, the costal margin at the base of the wing is slightly bent, the rest

Text-figs 35-36. *Cochylichroa atricapitana*; 35. wing pattern, 36. male genitalia (aedeagus on the left, valva on the right).

is convex, and the wing tip is short. The outer margin is convex. All veins are independent, chords, median and CuP vein missing. Nervula R5 ends at the costal margin before the wing tip. Nerve CuA2 originates between nerves R1 and R2. The background colour is yellowish-white or light yellow. The brown and black pattern consists of a broad basal patch, a median transverse band and a subapical band, both fragmented. The fringes are black.

Genitalia of male: tegumen is large and well sclerotized. Socii are rounded, and poorly sclerotized. The vinculum is strong, and its ventral branches are not fused. The valve has a short, concave costa, the apex of the valve is very narrow and rounded, sacculus is long, broad and rounded, lacking apophyses, on the internal surface of the valve an extensive territory is covered by small dentiform sclerites. Transtilla has narrow sides, and a narrow, pointed median part, juxta is simple. Aedeagus long, narrow and bent, terminal apophysis short and pointed, vesica with a cluster of small spines.

Genitalia of female: Anal papillae are short. Posterior and anterior apophyses are short. Tergite VIII is short. The sterigma is very broad and weakly sclerotized. The antrum is broad, with ventral and dorsal margins sclerotized. Ductus bursae are long, broad, and membranous, and corpus bursae are large, ovoid and membranous.

They are found primarily in North America, although *Cochylichroa atricapitana* is a Palearctic species.

78. *Cochylichroa atricapitana* (Stephens, 1852)

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VI, VII–IX. The larva monophagous on *Senecio jacobaea*. There are also reports of *Hypericum* and *Hieracium* plants, but this is disputed by many authors.

Habitat. We have little and incomplete knowledge of dry and mesophilic grasslands and roadside weed areas.

Range in Hungary. A total of 3 sites are known from the Hungarian Plain: Bátorliget (from 1948, Ferencszállás (from 1933, and more recently Jászberény (from 2009).

Distribution. From southwestern Siberia through Europe to Morocco. It is local and rare everywhere.

Remarks. Its rarity in Hungary has not yet been investigated.

***Brevicornutia* Razowski, 1960**

The genus is widespread in the western Palearctic.

Diagnosis of the adult. The labial palps are well developed, the second segment is much widened in its subterminal part, and the third segment is short. Antennae reach to the mid forewing. Forewing short and narrow, costal margin convex, wing tip short. The outer margin is convex (Fig. 300). All nerves are independent, chorda, median and CuP vein missing. Rib R5 ends on the costal margin before the wing tip. Nerve CuA2 originates between nerves R1 and R2. The background colour is yellowish-white, and the yellow, brown, and greyish pattern of various shades consists of a row of spots along the costal margin, a fragmented median transverse band and a subapical transverse band. The fringes are grey with a light-yellow basal line.

Genitalia of male. Tegumen is short and broad, well sclerotized. Uncus is missing, and so-cii are small and poorly sclerotized. The vinculum is strong, its ventral branches are not fused. The valve is narrow and elongated with a posteriorly oriented tip, sacculus is long with a terminal apophysis. Transtilla broad. Juxta is simple and flat. Aedeagus narrow at the coecum and much thickened at the distal end, with a sharp terminal apophysis. Vesica with a cluster of small horns. Caulis short.

Genitalia of female. Anal papillae normally conformation and short, anterior and posterior apophyses short. The sternum is weakly sclerotized. The antrum is broad, and best sclerotized of the whole genital armature. Bursa copulatrix has ductus bursae and corpus bursae membranosus, without signum.

79. *Brevicornutia pallidana* Zeller, 1847

Biology. Two generations yearly; V–VI, VII–VIII. The larvae are monophagous on *Jasione montana*.

Habitat. Shrublands, dry forest margins, marshlands, meadows and pastures of various types, pastures, rocky hillsides, and hillsides with grass, abandoned vineyards and orchards, etc.

Range in Hungary. Local occurrence up to 1000 m altitudes in hilly and mountainous areas. Only a highly isolated population is known in the lowland steppe zone.

Distribution. From the Primorsk region in Russia, through southern Siberia and Central Asia, to Scandinavia and the Iberian Peninsula as well as North Africa.

Remarks. According to observations from Germany (see Wegner 2011) adults are string on the flower heads or fly around in their close surroundings. The existence of inflorescences and seed heads of this host plant is essential, as the caterpillars develop in them in August and September. Intensive sheep grazing does not allow the species to develop. I have similar observations about intensively used mowed meadows and pastures in Southern Hungary.

Text-figs 37–38. *Brevicornutia pallidana*; 37. wing pattern, 38. male genitalia (aedeagus on the left, valva on the right). The valve is narrow and elongated.

Pontoturania Obraztsov, 1943

The genus name has not yet been used in Hungary. It is therefore important that researchers know it.

Diagnosis of Adults. Labial palps are well developed, the second segment much broadened in its subterminal part, third segment short. Antennae reach to the mid forewing. The forewing is short and narrow, and the costal margin at the base of the wing is slightly bent, otherwise, it is concave, and the tip of the wing is short. The outer margin is convex (Fig. 273-274). All veins are independent, chorda, median and CuP veins missing. The R5 nerve ends on the costal margin before the wing tip. Nerve CuA2 originates between nerves R1 and R2. The background colour is yellowish white. The brown and greyish pattern consists of a row of spots in the basal third of the costal margin, a fragmented median transverse band and a variable subapical transverse band. On the transverse bands, there may be greyish-plumb-urru patches with metallic lustre in *P. posterana*. The fringes are greyish.

Genitalia of male. The tegumen is short and broad, well sclerotized. The uncus is missing. Socii are small and poorly sclerotized. The vinculum is strong, its ventral branches are not fused. The valva is narrow and elongated, the costal margin concave, with a rounded tip, sacculus reaching to mid-valva and with a subterminal apophysis. Transtilla narrow, on the tip of the median side with a cluster of small spines. Juxta is simple and flat. The aedeagus was broad and long, with a long, bent terminal apophysis. Vesica with cornuti in the form of a dense group of long, thin spines. The caulis is long.

Genitalia of female. The anal papillae are normally shaped and short, the anterior and posterior apophyses are short. The sternum is weakly sclerotized. Antrum is broad, complex, best sclerotized of the entire genital armature. Bursa copulatrix has ductus bursae and corpus bursae membranous, without signum.

The genus is widespread in the Palearctic region, of the 8 described species only 2 are known in Europe and 1 in Hungary.

80. *Pontoturania posterana* Zeller, 1847

Biology. Bivoltine; V–VI, VII–VIII. The larva lives in the flowers and seeds of *Arctium lappa*, *A. tomentosum*, *Carduus acanthoides*, *C. nutans*, *Cirsium vulgare*, and *Jurinea cyanoides*.

Habitat. Meadows, grasslands, agricultural fallows, abandoned vineyards and thickets, lowland sand and steppe landscapes, arboretums, grassy ponds and near water banks, rocky grasslands on hillsides and mountainsides, karst scrub forests, forest clearings, forest edges, etc.

Range in Hungary. Widespread in many parts of the country, but mostly found in hilly and mountainous areas, with more local occurrences in the lowlands.

Distribution. From Iran through the Trans-Caspian region, it has been observed in many parts of Europe, as far west as the west coast and southwest to the Iberian Peninsula.

Remarks. A morphologically diverse species, it can be divided into several ecological forms.

Text-figs 39-40. *Pontoturania posterana*; 39. wing pattern, 40. male genitalia

***Cryptocochylis* Razowski, 1960**

Diagnosis of adults. The genus was first described by Józef Razowski in 1960. Labial palps are well developed, the second segment much broadened in its subterminal part, covered with long scales, third segment long, covered with small scales. Antennae reach halfway up the forewings.

The forewing is long and narrow, the costal margin at the base of the wing is concave, further on it is convex, and the tip of the wing is prominent. The outer margin is concave. All ribs are independent. The R5 rib ends on the outer margin below the wing tip. Vein CuA2 is short, bent and originates flush with vein R2.

Genitalia of male. Tegumen is large, well sclerotized, its distal part fused with narrow, weakly sclerotized partners. The vinculum is strong, and its ventral branches are not fused. Valva is triangular, with a broad base, tapering gradually towards the apex and terminating in a long, pointed terminal apophysis. At the base of the valve is a broad, serrated lobe. The sacculus is broad. The Transtilla has narrow lateral sides, a median side bifid, with two long, narrow, pointed branches. Juxta is simple with a rounded ventral margin. Aedeagus short, narrow and slightly bent, terminal apophysis short, broad and pointed, vesica without cornutus. Caulis is broad.

Genitalia of female. Anal papillae are short. The posterior and anterior apophyses are short and thick. Tergite VIII is short. Sterigma is very well represented, proximally it is membranous forming two sacks, has postero-lateral arms and a long median apophysis more strongly sclerotized. The antrum is narrow, cup-shaped, and masked by the sterigma. Ductus bursae are short, broad and weakly sclerotized, corpus bursae are large, ovoid and membranous, with signa formed by numerous small dentiform sclerites.

The species is local, with a western Palearctic range (Europe, Caucasus Mountains, and Asia Minor) (Razowski 2009).

81. *Cryptocochylis conjunctana* (Mann, 1864)

Biology. Adult flights are recorded from late April to late May. The food plant according to literature is *Achillea nobilis*.

Habitat. Dolomitic and volcanic rocky grasslands, karst scrub forests, abandoned old vineyards and fruit plantations.

Range in Hungary. Budapest (Sas-hegy), Göngyös (Sár-hegy), Gyöngyöstarján (Világos-hegy). No other sites are known.

Distribution. The Caucasus region Asia Minor and Dagestan. In Europe found in the Balkan Peninsula, Romania, Hungary Germany, and Italy.

Remarks. The first specimen was collected in 1914 on Sas-hegy in Budapest. After that, it was observed only in 2000 and 2008 in the southern foothills of the Mátra Mountains. The species is in a gradual regression in the Pannonian biogeographical region, endangered and deserving protection.

Text-fig. 41. *Cryptocochylis conjunctana*, the characteristic wing pattern

***Falseuncaria* Obraztsov & Swatschek, 1958**

Diagnosis of adults. Labial palps are well developed, the second segment much broadened in its subterminal part, third segment short, may be visible or completely masked by the long scales of the second segment. Antennae reach halfway up the forewings. The forewing is narrow and elongated, the costal margin is bent, and the wing tip is short. The outer margin is convex. All veins are independent. Median, chords and CuP vein missing. The R5 rib ends in the wing tip. The CuA2 rib originates between the R1 and R2 ribs. The background colour is light yellow. The yellowish-brown pattern consists of an elongated spot in the basal third of the costal margin, a median transverse band and a subapical transverse band. On the edges of the transverse bands, there are no greyish-plummy spots with metallic lustre. The fringes are light yellow brown.

Genitalia of male. Razowski (2009) presented the following male genital diagnosis: Facies similar to that of *Cochylis* but *Falseuncaria* with the distal part of the tegumen extending into a long process; the structures of the tegumen's apical portion include the fused socii. The structure of the sterigma and anterior membranous sack resemble *Cochylis*.

Genitalia of female. Posterior apophyses long, anterior apophyses short. Tergite VIII is long. Sterigma broad, weakly sclerotized. Antrum broad, well sclerotized. Ductus bursae membranous and narrow, corpus bursae ovoid, elongate, membranous, lacking signum.

The genus has 7 described species and is widespread in the Palaearctic and Africa.

82. *Falseuncaria degreyana* (Mc. Lachlan, 1869)

Biology. Collected specimens were found in April and August. The larvae live in the flower heads and seed capsules of *Plantago lanceolata*, *Linaria vulgaris*, and *Antirrhinum* according to the literature.

Habitat. Only a few places are known; mesophilic hill meadows, forest edges, dolomitic rocky grassland, and steppe slopes.

Range in Hungary. Only 3 sites are known; Budapest agglomeration (Budakeszi and Budáors) and South-Transdanubia (Kaposvár).

Distribution. According to Razowski (2009) a Europeo-Altai-Turanian zoogeographic element. Found in Europe from the Balkan Peninsula to Scandinavia and the British Isles, to the Iberian Peninsula.

Remarks. Hungarian observations are more than 70 years old, and no one has seen the species since. It is also possible that it has become extinct in the country because the sites around Budapest have been destroyed and built up.

Text-figs 42-43. *Falseuncaria degreyana*; 42. wing pattern, a rare, clear specimen, 43. male genitalia, aedeagus on the left, valva on the right.

83. *Falseuncaria ruficiliana* (Haworth, [1811])

Biology. Bivoltine; IV–VI, VII–VIII. Moths flying in September also occur. The larvae are polyphagous on *Antirrhinum*, *Aster*, *Bellis*, *Gentiana*, *Primula*, *Inula*, *Linaria*, and *Pedicularia* food plants etc.

Habitat. In a wide range of ecological environments, such as meadows and pastures, forest margins, rocky grasslands, karst scrub forests, scrub, grasslands etc.

Range in Hungary. Prefers hilly and mountainous areas, highly localised in lowland steppe areas. In the northern mountains, it reaches altitudes up to 1000 m.

Distribution. From the Amur region through southern Siberia, Central Asia and Asia Minor to the British Isles and Iberian Peninsula.

Remarks. One of the most widespread species in Hungary.

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Distribution maps 1-8: 1. *Phtheochroa inopiana*; 2. *P. schreibersiana*; 3. *P. pulvillana*; 4. *P. sodaliana*; 5. *P. fulvicinctana*; 6. *P. procerana*; 7. *P. purana*; 8. *P. duponchelana*

Distribution maps 9-16: 9. *Phtheochroa rugosana*; 10. *P. annae*; 11. *Hysteropha maculosana*; 12. *Cochylimorpha hilarana*; 13. *C. halophilana*; 14. *C. elongana*; 15. *C. perfusana*; 16. *C. subwolniana*

Distribution maps 17-24: 17. *Cochylimorpha woliniana*; 18. *C. obliquana*; 19. *C. jucundana*; 20. *C. straminea*; 21. *C. alternana*; 22. *Phalonidia gilvicomana*; 23. *Ph. curvistrigana*; 24. *Ph. udana*

Distribution maps 25-32: 25. *Phalonidia manniana*; 26. *Ph. affiniata*; 27. *Ph. albipalpana*;
 28. *Ph. contractana*; 29. *Gynnidomorpha luridana*; 30. *G. vectisana*;
 31. *G. minimana*; 32. *G. permixtana*

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Distribution maps 33-40: 33. *Gynnidomorpha alismana*; 34. *Agapeta hamana*;
35. *A. largana*; 36. *A. zoegana*; 37. *Fulvoclysia nerminae*; 38. *Eugnota lathoniana*;
39. *E. magnificana*; 40. *Prochlidonia amiantana*

Distribution maps 41-48: 41. *Eupoecilia angustana*; 42. *E. ambiguella*;
43. *E. sanguisorbana*; 44. *Aethes hartmanniana*; 45. *Ae. williana*; 46. *Ae. margarotana*;
47. *Ae. moribundana*; 48. *Ae. nefandana*

Distribution maps 49-56: 49. *Aethes margaritana*; 50. *Ae. triangulana*; *Ae. rutilana*; 52. *Ae. smeathmanniana*; 53. *Ae. tessera*; 54. *Ae. sanguinana*; *Ae. dilucidana*; 56a. *Ae. flagellana*; occurrence of the species in 1900, see the recent data on the next page.

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Distribution maps 56-63: 56b. *Aethes flagellana*; 57. *Ae. beatricella*;
58. *Ae. francillana*; 59. *Ae. bilbaensis*; 60. *Ae. tornella*; 61. *Ae. cnicana*;
62. *Ae. rubigana*; 63. *Ae. kindermanniana*

Distribution maps 64-71: 64. *Cochylidia rupicola*; 65. *C. subroseana*;
 66. *C. richteriana*; 67. *C. moguntiana*; 68. *C. heydeniana*; 69. *C. implicitana*;
 70. *Diceratura ostrinana*; 71. *Thyraylia nana*

Distribution maps 72-79: 72. *Cochylis roseana*; 73. *C. flaviciliana*;
 74. *Longicornutia epilina*; 75. *Neocochylis hybridella*; 76. *N. salebrana*; 77. *N. dubitana*
 78. *Cohylichroa atricapitana*; 79. *Brevicornutia pallidana*

Distribution maps 80-83: 80. *Pontoturania posterana*; 81. *Cryptocochylys conjunctana*;
82. *Falseuncaria degreyana*; 83. *F. ruficiliana*

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The list of references is by no means comprehensive but has been provided should the reader wish to enquire further into the various Cochylini species bionomic, taxonomy and distribution.

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